

Mass failure by rotational mechanism and surface erosion of homogenous soil slopes under varying steady unsaturated flow

Thanh Liem Vo ^a, Mohammad Rezaia ^{a,*}, Hesam Dejaloud ^a

David Airey ^b, Mohaddeseh Mousavi Nezhad ^c

^a School of Engineering, University of Warwick, Coventry, UK

^b School of Civil Engineering, University of Sydney, Sydney, New South Wales, Australia

^c Department of Civil & Environmental Engineering, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK

* Corresponding author

1 **Abstract**

2 Soil-borne pollutant is a major environmental concern in river systems. Mass failure and
3 surface erosion of stream banks represent major mechanisms by which contaminated topsoil
4 and subsurface layers are transported into rivers. Recent studies show that initially engineered
5 linear (planar) slopes, when subjected to hydromechanical loadings at the boundaries, change
6 to curvilinear (convex/concave) profiles. This study investigates and provides a new way to
7 quantify a steady state bound on the potential soil volume lost from riverbank as a consequence
8 of hydromechanical loading-induced changes to slope geometry via a rotational failure
9 mechanism and surface erosion. A two-dimensional (2D) formulation of Richards' (1931)
10 unsaturated flow equation is embedded within a Mohr-Coulomb limiting equilibrium analysis
11 framework and numerically solved for representative riverbank configurations. Results
12 indicate that for a bank height of 4 m, substantial volumes of soil (around 1.5-2.5 m³ per metre
13 run) are potentially erodible in typical sandy and silty clay banks of sufficiently high
14 permeability (to allow steady state condition to be established in the bank soils) due to moisture
15 movements between steady state infiltration and evaporation regimes. Variations in matric
16 head are generally most pronounced at slope crests, particularly in narrower banks. While
17 initially linear sandy and silty clay slopes both change to curvilinear shapes under limiting
18 equilibrium condition, steeper limiting geometries are observed in sandy slopes during
19 infiltrative condition, suggesting a dominant role of the friction angle, ϕ' , in governing the
20 slope shape at lower overall matric suction levels.

21

22 **Keywords:** Unsaturated flow, Mass failure, Surface erosion, Richards equation, Curvilinear
23 slope

24 **1. Introduction**

25 Pollution of river systems is a global concern, particularly pronounced in European river
26 networks and intensively cultivated regions. In Europe, rectification policies such as Directive
27 2000/60/EC (European Council, 2000) and Directive 2008/105/EC (European Council, 2008)
28 have been set up; however, almost half of European waterbodies have still been potentially
29 impacted by organic toxicants, including pesticides (Malaj et al. 2014, Moghimi et al. 2025).
30 More recent studies (Wolfram et al., 2021; Cooper and Hiscock, 2023) indicate that European
31 aquatic ecosystems remain acutely at risk from pesticide exposure. Multiple pathways
32 contribute to the transfer of pesticides into waterbodies, including spray drift (Schulz et al.,
33 2001), riverbank collapses (Fox et al., 2016; Ross et al., 2019), rainfall-induced run-off (Weibel
34 et al., 1964) and agricultural practices (Bennett et al., 2009; Stone et al., 2014), etc. Soil acts
35 as a major sink for pesticides (Moghimi et al. 2026), with certain compounds, such as persistent
36 organic pollutants (POPs), persisting in topsoil and subsurface layers for decades after their
37 last application (Gardes et al., 2021; Ivanova et al., 2021).

38 Soil-borne pollutants can be transported into rivers by different bank erosion processes
39 (Thorne, 1982; Lawler, 1992; Lawler, 1993): (1) mass failure (i.e., rotational failure, planar
40 failure and/or toppling), (2) surface erosion (i.e., run-off from rainfall, irrigation channel and/or
41 melting snow), and (3) subsurface erosion (e.g., suffosion, suffusion and/or piping). Mass
42 failure, in particular, can dominate sediment contributions, Simon and Darby (1999) estimated
43 that stream banks failure may account for up to 85% of sediment yield in many river systems.
44 Wilson et al. (2008), using radionuclide tracers, showed that 80% of stream sediment in five
45 agricultural watersheds originated from stream banks. Grove et al. (2013) estimated, from
46 LiDAR and aerial imagery analyses, that following the January 2011 storm in Queensland,
47 Australia, mass failures accounted for 41% of total eroded sediment along a 100 km stretch of
48 Lockyer Creek. Similarly, Fox et al. (2016) conducted a review of the literature on watershed-
49 scale sediment and nutrient loading from North American and European streambanks and
50 found that streambanks accounted for 6–93% of total phosphorus loads in streams. These
51 findings underscore the central role of mass failure mechanisms in sediment mobilisation and
52 reshaping landforms over time. However, research is scarce in showing how mass failure
53 mechanisms may be related to sediment yield and pesticide pollution in waterbodies, a
54 knowledge gap also highlighted in the review by Fox et al. (2016).

55 Several erosion models for European rivers have been developed at trench or segment scale,
56 addressing either transient flow events or steady state conditions informed by hydrological
57 cycles (Luppi et al., 2008; Chassiot et al., 2020; Duró et al., 2019; Duró et al., 2020). These
58 models often incorporate the extensive human modifications imposed on riverine environments
59 (Surian and Rinaldi, 2003; Lespez et al., 2015; Baena-Escudero et al., 2019; Madarino, 2022).
60 In terms of mass failure mechanisms, many process-based modelling approaches have been
61 proposed (Simon and Darby, 1999; Zhao et al., 2022). For any given location and time period,
62 the dominant mechanism depends on the size, geometry and structure of the bank, the
63 engineering properties of the bank materials (including their layering, anisotropic permeability
64 and strength) and riverside vegetation, the hydraulics of flow in the channel and climatic
65 conditions (Thorne, 1978; Simon and Darby, 1999; Hubble et al., 2010), and produces an
66 estimate of the potentially erodible soil volume, a key input into pollutant transport and mixing
67 models. For homogenous riverbank soil, a rotational failure is commonly taken as a reasonable
68 starting assumption.

69 Natural earth slopes, including riverbanks, have been described as planar (linear), convex or
70 concave (curvilinear) shapes (Gilbert, 1909; Cotton, 1952). Accelerated erosion tests in
71 laboratory settings (Bruthans et al., 2014) have demonstrated that a planar slope may change
72 to a concave or convex shape when continuously subjected to certain hydromechanical
73 loadings at the boundaries. Modelling studies further showed that by imposing limiting
74 equilibrium conditions on a slope without presupposing a geometry, a convex or concave shape
75 can be obtained as solution (Jeldes et al., 2014a; Vo and Russell, 2017). Evidence suggests that
76 concave slopes offer superior erosion resistance compared to planar and convex slopes (Young
77 and Mutchler, 1969a, 1969b; Meyer and Kramer, 1969; Rieke-Zapp and Nearing, 2005; Schor
78 and Gray, 2007; Jeldes et al., 2014b). Indeed, controlled field and laboratory trials (Martín-
79 Moreno et al., 2013; de Lima et al., 2018; Ao et al., 2021) showed reduced amounts of sediment
80 delivery by concave slopes. In the absence of anthropogenic modification, therefore, a concave
81 slope shape may be considered a reasonable starting point for calculating the amount of
82 sediment eroded from a homogenous riverbank soil under natural forces.

83 This paper presents a new method for quantifying the volume of soil mass potentially erodible
84 between two steady state flow and limiting equilibrium stress conditions. Riverbank soil is
85 assumed to be homogenous and of sufficiently high permeability (relative to the riverbank
86 environment's dynamics) for steady state flow conditions to be established. Riverbank slope at
87 a limiting equilibrium condition is assumed to be of curvilinear shape as shown in Fig. 1, and

88 the transition from one condition to the other is assumed to occur by either mass failure or
 89 surface erosion (i.e., subsurface erosion process is not considered here). The proposed method
 90 incorporates steady state flow conditions by solving Richards' equation for 2D unsaturated
 91 flow, and accounts for the stress limiting equilibrium condition of a Mohr-Coulomb soil using
 92 the slip line theory. When applied to riverbank materials involving strain softening and
 93 progressive failures, the theory can be useful in a limiting equilibrium approach with factor of
 94 safety for analysis and design, and is frequently utilised to establish bounds to true failure loads
 95 and mechanisms (Chen, 1975). Solutions of Richards' equation for one-dimensional (1D)
 96 unsaturated flow (where matric suction varies in the vertical direction but stay constant
 97 horizontally) have successfully been integrated into many limiting equilibrium analyses
 98 (Vahedifard et al., 2015; Vo and Russell, 2016; Vo and Russell, 2017; Peng and Vahedifard,
 99 2023; Jiang et al., 2024). To the best of the authors' knowledge, this represents the first attempt
 100 to couple a full 2D unsaturated flow formulation with a slip line theory-based elastoplastic soil
 101 strength reduction framework in assessing erodible soil mass from riverbank slopes under
 102 hydromechanical boundary conditions.

103

104

Figure 1. A simplified riverbank system considered for analysis.

105 2. Methodology

106 2.1. Initial problem geometry, flow parameters and boundary conditions

107 The homogenous soil slope considered is idealised as the side boundary (i.e., line AB) of a
108 trapezoidal soil domain ABCD shown in Fig 2(a). The trapezoid has bottom boundary and top
109 boundary of length $a/2$, $b/2$, respectively and it has a height of length L . The slope height L and
110 the slope inclination ($\angle ABC$) should be selected to match their respective measurements at a
111 particular site being analysed. The line CD is the symmetry axis, introduced by Tracey and
112 Vahedifard (2023) for mathematical tractability, and was directly related to their modelling of
113 a symmetric levee bank. In this problem, CD should be chosen to reflect a distance sufficiently
114 far from the riverbank where conditions approach 1-D, which should be at least several times
115 the thickness of the zone of variable matric suction (Fig. 2(b)) extended laterally from the crest
116 towards the interior. Although the slope AB is initially assumed to be linear, it is shown later
117 (see Section 2.3) that it must be of a curvilinear geometry to satisfy stress equilibrium and
118 boundary conditions.

119 The matric head is defined as $\psi = -s/\gamma_w$ (m) where s is matric suction (kN) and $\gamma_w = 9.81$
120 kN/m³ is the unit weight of water. The steady state water table W-W' is assumed to coincide
121 with the bottom boundary of the trapezoid, and a 2D coordinates system (x, z) is defined as
122 shown in Fig. 2(a), with z positive upwards from the water table.

123 The matric head on the slope surface, ψ_s , is assumed to vary linearly from 0 at the water table
124 to $c_1(-L)$ at height L where c_1 is a constant. As the distribution of matric suction above the
125 water table is complex even in a 1-D flow system (Fig. 2(b)), the constant c_1 should be selected
126 to match ψ_s as closely as possible with experimental measurements at a particular site.

127 The matric head on the top boundary is described by the function:

$$128 \psi_t = [c_2(-c_1L) + c_1L] \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{b} \left(x - \frac{a-b}{2} \right) \right] - c_1L, \frac{a-b}{2} \leq x \leq \frac{a+b}{2} \quad (1)$$

129 where c_2 is a constant. When $c_2 = 1$, ψ_t reduces to a constant, i.e., $\psi_t = c_1(-L)$ is imposed
130 throughout the top boundary. When $c_1 = c_2 = 1$, the condition of constant total head (rate $v =$
131 0 (m/s)) is imposed throughout the side and the top boundaries. Evaporative condition (flow
132 rate $v > 0$ (m/s)) and/or infiltrative condition (flow rate $v < 0$ (m/s)) (Griffiths and Lu, 2005) is
133 affected by varying c_1 and c_2 of the top and side boundary conditions. As with c_1 , the constant

134 c_2 should also be selected to match ψ_t as closely as possible with experimental measurements
 135 at a particular site.

136 It is noted that the top boundary condition ψ_t in Eq. 1 is expressed in terms of matric head to
 137 facilitate conversion between matric head, ψ , and matric suction, s . Since soil-atmosphere
 138 interactions (precipitation and evaporation) are physically flux-controlled processes, Appendix
 139 A shows how the top boundary condition can also be formulated in terms of flow rate v (m/s),
 140 and demonstrates this formulation via an example.

141

(b)

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143

144 **Figure 2. Initial geometry and flow boundary conditions of a riverbank slope: (a) Initial**
 145 **geometry and flow boundary conditions of a riverbank slope, (b) Typical variations of matric**
 146 **suction profile in soil far away from the slope edge.**

147 The model of Gardner (1958) is adopted to express how the hydraulic conductivity of the soil,
 148 k , and the effective degree of saturation, S_e , change with matric head:

$$149 \quad k = k_r k_{sat} = e^{(\alpha\psi)} k_{sat} \quad (2)$$

$$150 \quad S_e \equiv \frac{\theta - \theta_r}{\theta_s - \theta_r} = e^{(\alpha\psi)} \quad (3)$$

151 where k_r and k_{sat} are the relative and saturated hydraulic conductivity coefficients, respectively,
 152 and α is a constant dependent on soil type and state. θ , θ_s and θ_r are the volumetric water
 153 content corresponding to S_e , the saturated and the residual volumetric water contents,
 154 respectively. The approximation $\alpha \text{ (m}^{-1}\text{)} \approx 1/\left(\frac{s_e}{\gamma_w}\right) \text{ (m}^{-1}\text{)}$ is adopted here, where s_e denotes
 155 the air entry suction (s_{ae}) during drying (e.g., evaporation), and the air expulsion suction (s_{ex})
 156 during wetting (e.g., infiltration). The Gardner (1958) model (Eqs. 2 and 3) are often used to
 157 facilitate (semi-)analytical investigations of unsaturated flow problems and to verify complex
 158 numerical results (Tracey, 2006; Tracey and Vahedifard, 2023). At lower range of matric
 159 suction (as are most cases being analysed here), this simple model matched experimental data

160 reasonably (Ghezzehei et al., 2007) compared with more flexible models such as the van
 161 Genuchten (1980) model. Extension to the Gardner (1958) model would be required to account
 162 for soils on the drying-wetting scanning paths and/or with significant soil structure dependency.

163 Based on Eqs. 2 and 3, the spatial distribution of matric head within the soil domain ABCD
 164 can be described by the 2D form of the Richards equation (Richards, 1931) as:

$$165 \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(k_{\text{sat}} e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(k_{\text{sat}} e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} k_{\text{sat}} e^{\alpha\psi} = e^{\alpha\psi} \left[\frac{\partial\theta_s}{\partial t} + \alpha(\theta_s - \theta_r) \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} \right] \quad (4)$$

166 Assuming that volumetric water content, θ_s , is approximately a constant, $\frac{\partial\theta_s}{\partial t} \approx 0$ so Eq. 4 can
 167 be reduced to:

$$168 \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} e^{\alpha\psi} = \frac{\alpha(\theta_s - \theta_r)}{k_{\text{sat}}} e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial t} \quad (5)$$

169 The initial condition for Eq. 5 is set at:

$$170 \quad \psi(x, z, 0) = -z \quad (6)$$

171 At steady state condition, Eq. 5 becomes:

$$172 \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(e^{\alpha\psi} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} e^{\alpha\psi} = 0 \quad (7)$$

173 By introducing the change of variable $\bar{\psi} = e^{\alpha\psi} - e^{-\alpha z}$, Eqs. 5 and 7 can be rewritten,
 174 respectively, in the following form (Tracy and Vahedifard, 2023):

$$175 \quad \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{\psi}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\psi}}{\partial z^2} \right) + \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} = \frac{(\theta_s - \theta_r)}{k_{\text{sat}}} \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial t} \quad (8)$$

$$176 \quad \frac{1}{\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \bar{\psi}}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \bar{\psi}}{\partial z^2} \right) + \frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (9)$$

177 Given the defined transformed potential, $\bar{\psi}$, above, and from Eq. 1, the top boundary condition
 178 becomes:

$$179 \quad \bar{\psi}_t = e^{\alpha \left\{ [c_2(-c_1L) + c_1L] \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{b} \left(x - \frac{a-b}{2} \right) \right] - c_1L \right\}} - e^{-\alpha L} \quad (10)$$

180 Similarly, using the defined transformed potential and the side boundary expression $\psi_s =$
 181 $-c_1z$, the side (slope) boundary condition becomes:

$$182 \quad \bar{\psi}_s = e^{\alpha(-c_1z)} - e^{-\alpha z} \quad (11)$$

183 Likewise, given that the matric head is zero at the water table ($z = 0$), the bottom boundary
184 condition becomes:

$$185 \quad \bar{\psi}_b = e^0 - e^0 = 0 \quad (12)$$

186 In terms of $\bar{\psi}$, the initial condition set in Eq. 6 is expressed as:

$$187 \quad \bar{\psi}(x, z, 0) = 0 \quad (13)$$

188 The solution in terms of $\bar{\psi}$ can be converted back to the matric head, ψ , using:

$$189 \quad \psi = \frac{1}{\alpha} \ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}) \quad (14)$$

190

191 **2.2. Influence of initial geometry and flow parameters on the matric head distribution** 192 **within a linear slope**

193 Eqs. 8 and 9, together with the associated boundary and initial conditions (Eqs. 10-13), are
194 solved numerically in MATLAB R2018b using the finite element method for a range of
195 geometry and boundary condition variations. For verification, the adopted numerical
196 procedures are used to calibrate against results reported by Tracey and Vahedifard (2023). The
197 parameters for this calibration are listed under case no. 1 in Table 1. Subsequently, additional
198 simulations (case nos. 2-6 in Table 1) are carried out to explore the influence of the bank
199 dimension b and flow parameters on the steady state and time dependent distributions of matric
200 head within a linear riverbank slope. In cases 3-6, the slope height L of 4 m and the slope
201 inclination $\angle ABC$ of 45° are chosen to represent an actively eroding European riverbank, as
202 measurements from several studies (Thorne, 1978; Casagli et al., 1999; Luppi et al., 2008;
203 Klösch et al., 2011; Veihe et al. 2011; Anstead et al., 2012; Jugie et al., 2018; Augustowski
204 and Kukulak, 2021) indicate that they vary significantly in height (e.g., between 1.2 m and 6.4
205 m based on the summary in Table 3), and are fairly steep (e.g., loam/clay loam banks' average
206 inclination of 40° (Veihe et al., 2011), up to 45° inclination in non-cohesive layers and higher
207 in cohesive layers (Thorne, 1978)).

208 Fig. 3(a) shows the variation of relative permeability, k_r , with matric suction, s , for a typical
209 sand and a typical silty clay undergoing drying and wetting, by the Gardner 1958 model (Eq.
210 2) as used in this analysis (nearly identical curves could be obtained by the van Genuchten
211 (1980) model with $n_{vG} = 1.95$, $m_{vG} = 1 - \frac{1}{n_{vG}} = 0.487$ and $\alpha_{vG} \approx \frac{\alpha}{1.3n_{vG}}$ (Ghezzehei et al.,

212 2007) where $n_{vG}, m_{vG}, \alpha_{vG}$ are parameters of the van Genuchten (1980) model). The air-
213 expulsion values, s_{ex} , of the typical sand and the typical silty clay are taken as 3 kPa and 15
214 kPa, respectively. The air-entry values, s_{ae} , of the typical sand and the typical silty clay are
215 taken as 10 kPa and 50 kPa, respectively. The soil is assumed to be on the main drying curve
216 corresponding to its evaporative condition, and on the main wetting curve corresponding to its
217 infiltrative condition. The (s, k_r) values at points A and D (Fig. 2(a)) for cases 3-6 (Table 1) are
218 indicated in Fig. 3(a).

219 Figs. 3(b) and 3(c) illustrate the steady state flow boundary conditions being applied along the
220 side boundary (line AB in Fig. 2(a)) and the top boundary (line AD in Fig. 2(a)) of case nos.
221 3-6 (Table 1). In Figs. 3(b) and 3(c), the subscripts 3, 4, 5, 6 are attached to points A, B, D to
222 indicate the analysis case number. For the flow parameters adopted in the analysis, cases 3 and
223 5 lie entirely in the infiltrative domain, case 6 in the evaporative domain and case 4 in both
224 evaporative and infiltrative domains. Due to the suction variation near the point of saturation
225 for the typical sand in case 4 being relatively small (7 kPa maximum), and the lengthy
226 experimentation required to precisely determine the typical sand's wetting-drying scanning
227 path, the hydraulic state of this case is assumed to be on the drying curve corresponding to its
228 evaporative condition (Fig. 3(a)) for computation. In addition, a typical sand would be
229 sufficiently free draining to establish a steady state matric suction profile such as the one
230 assumed in Fig. 2(a) relatively quickly. However, the time required to reach steady state in the
231 silty clay might exceed the duration or flood or precipitation events and may create critical
232 transient conditions leading to slope instability (Morgenstern, 1963). Consequently, transient
233 state analyses are conducted for the typical silty clay (cases 5 and 6 in Table 1) for $k_{sat} =$
234 10^{-5} m/s and $k_{sat} = 10^{-7}$ m/s to examine the silty clay slope's time-dependent responses.

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Figure 3. Simplified hydraulic conductivity functions and flow boundary conditions used in analysis: (a) Simplified hydraulic conductivity functions, (b) Side and top boundary conditions of the typical sand (case 3, case 4), (c) Side and top boundary conditions of the typical silty clay (case 5, case 6).

243 Analysis cases are summarised in Table 1.

244

Table 1. Analysis parameters of flow through initially linear slope.

Case no.	Material	Flow condition [†]	k_{sat}	$\theta_s : \theta_r$	s_e	$\alpha = 1 / \left(\frac{s_e}{\gamma_w} \right)^{\dagger\dagger}$	$c_1 : c_2$	$a : b : L$
			(m/s)	(-):(-)	(kPa)	(1/m)		
1 [§]	n. a.	n. a.	10^{-6}	0.4:0	n. a.	0.001	1:0.25	100:80:40
2 ^{§§}	n. a.	n. a.	10^{-6}	0.4:0	n. a.	0.001	1:0.25	1000:980:40
3	Typical sand	Infiltrative	n. a.	n. a.	$s_{ex}=3$	3.27	0.051:0 [‡]	30:22:4
4	Typical sand	Evaporative and infiltrative	n. a.	n. a.	$s_{ae}=10$	0.981	0.255:6.8 [*]	30:22:4
5	Typical silty clay	Infiltrative	10^{-7} - 10^{-5}	0.5:0.2	$s_{ex}=15$	0.654	0.255:0 [‡]	30:22:4

6	Typical silty clay	Evaporative	10^{-7} - 10^{-5}	0.5:0.2	$s_{ae}=50$	0.196	1.274:6.8*	30:22:4
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245 § for calibration against results of Tracey and Vahedifard (2023).

246 §§ an expansion of the calibrated result of Tracey and Vahedifard (2023) in case 1, to assess the influence of the magnitude of
 247 the riverbank dimension b .

248 † flow state is taken to be on the drying curve during evaporation and the wetting curve during infiltration, hydraulic
 249 hysteresis is not considered in Tracey and Vahedifard (2023) hence flow state not considered in cases 1 and 2.

250 †† α is a fitting parameter in Tracey and Vahedifard (2023) hence s_e not considered in cases 1 and 2.

251 ‡ c_1 is selected such that $c_1 L = s_{ex} / \gamma_w$, c_2 is selected such that $c_2 (-c_1 * L) = 0$.

252 * c_1 is selected such that $c_1 L = s_{ae} / \gamma_w$, c_2 is selected such that $\psi_t = (68 / \gamma_t)$ at D in case 4 and $= (340 / \gamma_t)$ at D in case 6.

253 2.3. Steady state geometry, stress parameters and boundary conditions

254 The linear slope in Fig. 2(a) would change to a curvilinear profile to satisfy stress equilibrium
 255 and boundary conditions. There are experimental evidences (Martín-Moreno et al., 2013; de
 256 Lima et al., 2018; Ao et al., 2021) demonstrating superior performance of curvilinear slopes
 257 (compared to linear slopes) in limiting sediment runoff. Fig. 4(a) shows an idealised curvilinear
 258 slope changed from the linear configuration in Fig. 2(a), together with the associated stress
 259 boundary conditions. The flow boundary conditions are the same as those defined in Section
 260 2.1.

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263 **Figure 4. Steady state geometry and stress boundary conditions of a riverbank slope: (a) Steady**
 264 **state geometry and stress boundary conditions of a riverbank slope, (b) Boundary conditions**
 265 **imposed at the slope surface.**

266 The soil body ABCD is assumed to be homogenous (for soils containing different layers and/or
 267 admissible stress discontinuities, extensions to this slip line analysis, e.g. Sokolovskii (1965)
 268 (p. 156), Vo and Russell (2020), would be required) and consists of three regions representing
 269 different stress states: (1) region OBE at the state of limiting equilibrium, (2) region EBCF
 270 which is not at the state of limiting equilibrium and (3) region AOEFD which is a non-limiting
 271 cracked soil layer of depth h_0 (i.e., the shaded area in Fig. 4(a)). The limiting shear strength
 272 (according to the Mohr-Coulomb criterion) is not mobilised in the cracked soil. However,
 273 region AOEFD contributes to region OBE failing in a rotational mechanism (about the toe B)
 274 by exerting a surcharge q on OE (Sokolovskii, 1965; Vo and Russell, 2017). No other
 275 surcharge is considered in this paper. OA is assumed to be vertical. Similar to Fig. 2(a), the
 276 line CD should be chosen to reflect a distance sufficiently far from the riverbank where
 277 conditions approach 1-D.

278 Adopting Bishop's (1959) effective stress concept for unsaturated soils, the static equilibrium
 279 of a soil element obeying Mohr-Coulomb criterion, in the region OBE, can be expressed along
 280 two stress characteristic families $\langle \eta \rangle$ and $\langle \xi \rangle$ (Vo and Russell, 2016) as:

281 Along the stress family $\langle \eta \rangle$:

$$282 \quad dx = \tan \left[\theta_p + \left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\phi'}{2} \right) \right] dz \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
283 \quad d\sigma'_m + 2 \tan \varphi' \sigma'_m d\theta_p &= \left[\gamma_t + \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z} \right] (dz - \tan \varphi' dx) + \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x} (dz + \\
284 \quad \tan \varphi' dx) & \quad \quad \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

285 Along the stress family $\langle \zeta \rangle$:

$$286 \quad dx = \tan \left[\theta_p - \left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\varphi'}{2} \right) \right] dz \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
287 \quad d\sigma'_m - 2 \tan \varphi' \sigma'_m d\theta_p &= \left[\gamma_t + \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z} \right] (dz - \tan \varphi' dx) - \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x} (dz - \\
288 \quad \tan \varphi' dx) & \quad \quad \quad (18)
\end{aligned}$$

289 where the variables σ'_m and θ_p denote the mean effective stress and the angle between the
290 vertical axis (z) and the major principal stress direction, respectively. The parameters c' and φ'
291 are effective cohesion and effective friction angle of the soil at Mohr-Coulomb limiting
292 condition, while χ and γ_t denote the effective stress parameter (Bishop, 1959) and the soil's
293 bulk unit weight, respectively. χ depends on many factors such as soil structure, degree of
294 saturation, drying-wetting cycle and stress history (Bishop, 1961). For simplicity, c' , φ' and
295 γ_t are assumed constant throughout the soil body. χs is an empirically determined term referred
296 to as the contribution of suction to the effective stress and varies spatially depending on the
297 effective stress parameter χ and the distribution of matric head ψ . As Mohr-Coulomb is a
298 perfectly elastic-plastic model, consideration of the impact of strain-softening behavior driven
299 by post-peak strength reduction and stress redistribution (Rowe and Peaker, 1965; Troncone,
300 2005) is accounted for by suitable section of c' , φ' (e.g., c' , φ' is commonly reduced by factor
301 > 1 in designing a stable (non-limiting) slope).

302 The model of Khalili and Khabbaz (1998) is adopted to express the effective stress parameter
303 as:

$$304 \quad \chi = 1, s < s_e; \chi = \left(\frac{s}{s_e} \right)^{-0.55}, s \geq s_e \quad (19)$$

305 Eq. 19 can be readily adapted to a limiting equilibrium framework, and it has been calibrated
306 extensively against experimental data (e.g., Khalili and Khabbaz, 1998; Khalili and
307 Zargarbashi, 2010; Vo et al., 2020). Eq. 19 is only applicable to soils on the drying or the
308 wetting paths. As in Section 2.1, s_e is the air entry suction (s_{ae}) when the soil undergoes drying
309 (e.g., during evaporation), and s_e is the air expulsion suction (s_{ex}) when the soil undergoes
310 wetting (e.g., during infiltration). Extensions to Eq. 19 (e.g., Khalili and Zargarbashi, 2010;

311 Wang et al., 2024) would be required to account for soils on the drying-wetting scanning paths
 312 and/or with significant soil structure dependency.

313 Since OA is vertical, the depth h_0 (Fig. 4(a)) is the maximum height of a limiting vertically
 314 faced cracked soil layer. The surcharge q_{OE} is taken to arise from the weight of this cracked
 315 soil layer. When the cracks do not contain water, it can be shown using limit analyses (Chen
 316 and Scawthorn, 1970; Michalowski, 2013) incorporating the effective stress concept for
 317 unsaturated soils (Bishop, 1959) that h_0 is bounded by a lower bound and an upper bound as:

$$318 \frac{2[(\chi s)_{OE} + c' \cot \varphi'] \sin \varphi'}{\gamma_t(1 - \sin \varphi')} \leq \left(h_0 = \frac{q_{OE}}{\gamma_t} \right) \leq \frac{3.83[(\chi s)_{OE} + c' \cot \varphi'] \sin \varphi'}{\gamma_t(1 - \sin \varphi')} \quad (20)$$

319 As the slip line theory often gives very close or identical solutions to those derived by the lower
 320 bound theorem of limit analysis (Chen, 1975), the lower bound on h_0 in Eq. 20 is adopted in
 321 this paper, i.e.,

$$322 h_0 = \frac{2[(\chi s)_{OE} + c' \cot \varphi'] \sin \varphi'}{\gamma_t(1 - \sin \varphi')} \quad (21)$$

323 Eq. (21) expresses h_0 's dependency on soil parameters c' , φ' , γ_t and $(\chi s)_{OE}$. Influence of flow
 324 conditions on h_0 can be captured by the χ model of Eq. 19 (in this study) or alternatives (e.g.,
 325 Bishop, 1959; Lu et al., 2010; Khalili and Zargarbashi, 2010).

326 The line OE in Fig. 4(a) is the boundary between the soil region OBE at limiting equilibrium
 327 condition and the non-limiting cracked soil layer of depth h_0 . For the soil region OBE at
 328 limiting equilibrium condition, the boundary conditions on OE are:

$$329 \theta_p = 0 \quad (22)$$

$$330 \sigma'_m = \frac{q_{OE} + (\chi s)_{OE} + c' \cot \varphi'}{1 + \sin \varphi'} \quad (23)$$

331 where q_{OE} and $(\chi s)_{OE}$ are surcharge and contribution of suction to the effective stress along OE,
 332 respectively.

333 The curvilinear slope geometry is not known initially. It is obtained by solving the 3rd boundary
 334 value problem type (Sokolovskii, 1965) for the soil region next to the slope surface (i.e., the
 335 shaded area in Fig. 4(b)). It requires the following boundary conditions to be imposed on the
 336 slope OB (Fig. 4(a), with more details in Fig. 4(b)):

$$337 \frac{dx}{dz} = \tan \theta_p \quad (24)$$

338
$$\sigma'_m = \frac{\chi s + c' \cot \varphi'}{1 - \sin \varphi'} \quad (25)$$

339 Eq. 24 is a physically derived boundary condition as it requires the slope curvature itself to
 340 coincide with the major principal stress direction (i.e., the direction on which normal stress is
 341 at its maximum compressive value (as shown in the close-up view of point S in Fig. 4(b)), and
 342 Eq. 25 expresses the magnitude of the mean effective stress on the slope surface.

343 The boundary conditions at point O are:

344
$$x = \frac{a-b}{2}, z = L - h_0 \quad (26)$$

345 **2.4. Influence of steady state flow and mechanical parameters on the shape of a**
 346 **curvilinear slope**

347 Eqs. 15-18 together with associated boundary conditions (Eqs. 22-26) are numerically solved
 348 in MATLAB R2018b using the finite difference scheme of Sokolovskii (1965) for cases 3-6
 349 with the geometric parameters listed in Table 1, but now with the additional mechanical
 350 parameters listed in Table 2. More specifically, the matric head field $\psi(x, z)$, obtained from
 351 the flow analysis, is used to compute the spatial derivatives $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x}$, $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z}$ which
 352 appear in the governing limiting equilibrium equations 16 and 18. Since c' , φ' are constants
 353 (Table 2) and the χ model adopted (Eq. 19) is a simple function of s and s_e , the derivatives
 354 $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z}$ can be written as exact expressions of $\psi(x, z)$ or $\bar{\psi}(x, z)$ (as
 355 shown in Appendix B). The finite difference scheme uses these derivatives to compute a
 356 curvilinear slope geometry. This updated geometry is then reintroduced into the flow analysis
 357 of Section 2.1 to generate a new matric head field, $\psi(x, z)$, which is subsequently applied in
 358 the mechanical analysis of Section 2.3. This process is repeated iteratively to the point when
 359 negligible change is observed in both geometry and the matric head field $\psi(x, z)$. The iterative
 360 calculation procedure and the convergence criterion on the geometry are illustrated in Fig. 5.
 361 For this investigation, a mesh of 150 $\langle \eta \rangle$ characteristics by 150 $\langle \xi \rangle$ characteristics are used to
 362 numerically integrate the slip line governing equations (Eqs. 15-18) together with associated
 363 boundary conditions (Eqs. 22-26) from the soil surface boundary OE to the slope surface
 364 boundary OB. Convergence on each $(\sigma'_m, \theta_p, x, z)$ solution point is achieved when the following
 365 criteria (Eqs. 27-30) are all met:

366
$$\left| \frac{(\sigma'_m)_{i+1} - (\sigma'_m)_i}{(\sigma'_m)_i} \right| < 0.0001 \quad (27)$$

367
$$\left| \frac{(\theta_p)_{i+1} - (\theta_p)_i}{(\theta_p)_i} \right| < 0.0001 \quad (28)$$

368
$$\left| \frac{(x)_{i+1} - (x)_i}{(x)_i} \right| < 0.0001 \quad (29)$$

369
$$\left| \frac{(z)_{i+1} - (z)_i}{(z)_i} \right| < 0.0001 \quad (30)$$

370 The subscripts $i+1$ and i in Eqs. 27-30 denote current and previous calculation step,
 371 respectively. Additional details on Sokolovskii's (1965) finite difference scheme's
 372 implementation have been reported in Vo and Russell (2016) and Vo and Russell (2020). As
 373 the iterative calculation procedure is limited to the steady state, complex transient state effects
 374 such as mechanical unloading impacts on the water retention curve, porosity, and suction
 375 changes due to stress release have not been accounted for during the iteration.

376

377 **Figure 5. The iterative calculation procedure (at steady state) adopted in this study.**

378 To ensure numerical accuracy, the analysis of case 7 (Table 2) is conducted to calibrate against
 379 the curvilinear slope profile results of Jeldes et al. (2014a) and Vo and Russell (2017). For this
 380 calibration, the flow parameters of a typical silt ($\alpha = 0.3924$ (1/m), $c_1 = 0.637$, $c_2 = 1$) are
 381 used to obtain a $\chi s(x, z)$ field where the vertical variation of χs is similar to the linear function
 382 adopted by Vo and Russell (2017).

383 **Table 2. Analysis parameters of flow through curvilinear slope at limiting condition.**

Case no.	Material	φ'	c'	γ_t	$a : b : L$
----------	----------	------------	------	------------	-------------

		(°)	(kPa)	(kN/m ³)	(m):(m):(m)
3**	Typical sand	40	1	18	30:22:4
4**	Typical sand	40	1	18	30:22:4
5**	Typical silty clay	25	2	16	30:22:4
6**	Typical silty clay	25	2	16	30:22:4
7**	Typical fine-grained soil	30	30	15	1000:920.6:53

384 ** Mohr-Coulomb shear strength parameters (c' , ϕ') adopted in this study are more typical of those values
385 mobilised at critical state strain level.

386 ** for calibration against the curvilinear slope profile results of Jeldes et al. (2014a) and Vo and Russell (2017)
387 only, more realistic riverbank geometry (especially L) and soil properties (especially c') would be significantly
388 different.

389

390 **3. Results and discussion**

391 **3.1. Influence of initial geometry and flow parameters on the distribution of matric** 392 **head within a linear slope**

393 The results of calibrating cases 1 and 2 (Table 1) are presented in Fig. 6. The contours plotted
394 in the figure show the matric head (m) distributions within a linear slope at 1 day (Fig. 6(a)),
395 at 2 days (Fig. 6(b)) and at steady state (Fig. 6(c)). In case 1, the results obtained differ slightly
396 at 1 and 2 days to those of Tracey and Vahedifard (2023) for the same geometry and flow
397 parameters in their analysis. This is likely to be due to the elastic deformation effect
398 incorporated into Tracey and Vahedifard (2023)'s analytical model but not accounted for in the
399 present study. This effect vanishes at steady state, so the two sets of results become nearly
400 identical as shown in Fig. 6(c).

401 Also, comparison of the two cases shows that when the slope width is much larger (case 2 with
402 $b=980$ m, compared to case 1 with $b=80$ m), the matric head change towards the slope crest is
403 markedly milder as expected.

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Figure 6. Matric head ψ distributions (m) of Tracey and Vahedifard (2023), case 1 and case 2 (Table 1): (a) at 1 day, (b) at 2 days, (c) at steady state.

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The steady state results of cases 3 and 4 (Table 1) for a typical sandy slope are shown in Fig. 7(a), and those of cases 5 and 6 (Table 1) for a typical silty clay slope are shown in Fig. 7(b). The contours in both figures show matric head (m) distributions within linear slopes, and their patterns are regulated by the exponential form of the Gardner (1959) model (Eq. 2). The 4 m height of the linear slopes considered in cases 3-6 is representative of European riverbanks compared to the 40 m slope height considered in cases 1 and 2 which was used mainly for numerical calibration against the literature. Figs. 7 show more negative matric head values within the typical silty clay slope than the typical sandy slope during either infiltration or evaporation, as expected from their different imposed flow boundary conditions.

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The transient state analysis results are shown in Figs. 7(c) and 7(d) for a typical silty clay slope undergoing infiltration (case 5 in Table 1) and in Figs. 7(e) and 7(f) for undergoing evaporation (case 6 in Table 1). The matric head distributions within the silty clay slope are shown to reach approximately steady state conditions after just 1 day for $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-5}$ m/s (Figs. 7(c) and 7(e)) whereas much longer times (> 30 days) are needed for $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-7}$ m/s (Figs. 7(d) and 7(f)). It is noted that these calculated times are specific to the adopted geometry, boundary conditions and the initial condition set in Eq. 13. Nevertheless, they highlight how a low k_{sat} of the typical silty clay (and other fine-grained soils more generally) could drastically increase the dissipation time needed to reach a steady state condition within a riverbank slope after a significant flux (infiltrative/evaporative) event.

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 435 **Figure 7. Matric head ψ distributions (m) of typical sand and typical silty clay: (a)**
 436 **Typical sand (case 3, case 4) at steady state, (b) Typical silty clay (case 5, case 6) at**
 437 **steady state, (c) Typical silty clay (case 5, $k_{sat} = 10^{-5}$ m/s) towards steady state, (d)**
 438 **Typical silty clay (case 5, $k_{sat} = 10^{-7}$ m/s) towards steady state, (e) Typical silty clay**
 439 **(case 6, $k_{sat} = 10^{-5}$ m/s) towards steady state, (f) Typical silty clay (case 6, $k_{sat} =$**
 440 **10^{-7} m/s) towards steady state.**

441 **3.2. Influence of steady state flow and mechanical parameters on the shape of a**
 442 **curvilinear slope**

443 This section shows the results of the coupled steady state flow-mechanical analyses described
 444 in Section 2.4, once the convergence criterion on the geometry (Fig. 5) has been numerically
 445 met, applicable to those cases in practice where steady state flow field can be established
 446 quickly relative to occurrences of significant flux events (i.e. the typical sand and the typical
 447 silty clay with relatively high k_{sat}).

448 The analysis results of case 7 (Table 2) and the iterative sequence to obtain the final curvilinear
 449 slope profile are respectively presented in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b), which show the χ_s (kPa)
 450 distributions. In Fig. 8(a), the curvilinear slope profile of case 7 is different from that obtained
 451 by Vo and Russell (2017) (p. 550) where the 1D profile $\chi_s=20-0.1[(53-6.93)-z]$ (kPa), together
 452 with a uniform surcharge of $q= 30$ kPa were considered. Both profiles (case 7 and the one in
 453 Vo and Russell (2017)) are steeper than the profile from the dry soil condition ($\chi_s=0$ kPa)

454 assumed by Jeldes et al. (2014a). Since c' , φ' and γ_t and the slope height (= 53 m) are identical
 455 across these analyses, the differences in the obtained curvilinear slope profiles can be attributed
 456 to the influence of different χ_s profiles on the strength of the soil and the overall slope. Fig.
 457 8(b) shows that the initial guess $OE'=15$ m results in a curvilinear slope geometry which does
 458 not meet the convergence criterion adopted (Fig. 5) while the final guess $OE'=15.2$ m results
 459 in a satisfactory geometry. A few cycles of iteration are necessary for the problem in this study;
 460 however, utilising an algorithm such as Vo et al. (2022) may be required for problems with
 461 more parameters and/or more complex convergence criteria.

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464 **Figure 8. Steady state curvilinear slope profiles of case 7 (Table 2): (a) Curvilinear slope**
 465 **profile of case 7, Jeldes et al. (2014a) and Vo and Russell (2017), contours show the χ_s**
 466 **distribution (kPa) of case 7, (b) Iterative sequence to obtain the final curvilinear slope**
 467 **profile of case 7 (on the boundary OE, h_0 (calculated from Eq. 21) changes in response**
 468 **to spatial χ_s variation).**

469 The results of cases 3 and 4 (Table 2) for the typical sand are shown in Fig. 9(a), and those of
 470 cases 5 and 6 (Table 2) for the typical silty clay are shown in Fig. 9(b). The contours in these
 471 two figures illustrate the χ_s (kPa) distributions within the curvilinear slopes. Figs. 9 show
 472 higher χ_s values in the typical silty clay than in the typical sand under both infiltration and
 473 evaporation. For both soil types, the length of the vertical segment h_0 is significantly greater
 474 under evaporation than infiltration, as expected. In Fig. 9(b), the entire slope surface is vertical
 475 for the typical silty clay under evaporation (case 6). This is due to h_0 exceeding L ($= 4$ m) in
 476 case 6, which can be shown by rewriting Eq. 21 as:

$$477 \quad (\chi_s)_{OE} = \frac{h_0 \gamma_t (1 - \sin \varphi')}{2 \sin \varphi'} - c' \cot \varphi' \quad (31)$$

478 Fig. 10(a) plots $\frac{d(\chi_s)_{OE}}{dh_0}$ for $\varphi' = 20^\circ$ to 45° , $\gamma_t = 16$ and 18 kN/m³ based on Eq. 31. It shows that
 479 for Mohr-Coulomb soils, the impact of a change in χ_s on a change in h_0 is greater (i.e., the χ_s
 480 $\sim h_0$ relation is more sensitive) in a typical silty clay slope (cases 3 and 4) than in a typical sand
 481 slope (cases 5 and 6). Fig. 10(b) plots χ_s contours given by Eq. 31 for different combinations
 482 of c' and φ' , $h_0 = 4$ m and the approximation $\gamma_t = 17$ kN/m³. It shows that $\chi_s \geq 17.7$ kPa and χ_s
 483 ≥ 42.2 kPa are required to maintain a limiting vertically faced 4 m soil layer located at the top
 484 of a typical sandy riverbank and a typical silty clay riverbank, respectively. Fig. 10(c) plots χ_s
 485 contours given by the χ model of Eq. 19 and the χ_s applied at the top boundary in cases 3-4 (for
 486 the typical sand) and cases 5-6 (for the typical silty clay). It shows that when χ_s does not vary
 487 significantly within the cracked soil layer, the χ_s applied along the boundary AD (see Fig. 2(a))
 488 of the typical silty clay under evaporation (case 6) is greater than the 42.2 kPa required for the
 489 stability of a 4 m long vertically faced soil layer. In comparison, the χ_s applied along the left
 490 part (including point A) of the boundary AD of the typical sand under infiltration and
 491 evaporation (case 4) is smaller than 17.7 kPa, thus Fig. 9(a) shows that a curvilinear slope
 492 segment necessarily locates below the h_0 long vertically faced soil layer. Fig. 10(c) show that
 493 the χ_s applied along the boundary AD is smaller than 17.7 kPa for the typical sand under
 494 infiltration (case 3) and smaller than 42.2 kPa for the silty clay under infiltration (case 5), a
 495 curvilinear slope segment exists below the vertical segment h_0 in case 3 (Fig. 9(a)) and case 5

496 (Fig. 9(b)) accordingly. This result suggests that a vertically faced soil layer of significant
 497 height (e.g., $L=4$ m in case 6) can exist if the steady state χ_s applied to its boundaries is
 498 sufficiently large (e.g., in slopes consisting of fine-grained soils undergoing predominantly
 499 evaporative conditions). Whether such a χ_s can be sustained over the long term would depend
 500 strongly on the level of desiccation cracking and progressive tensile failures which occur in
 501 many fine-grained riverbanks.

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504 **Figure 9. Curvilinear slope profiles of typical sand and typical silty clay at steady state**
 505 **conditions, contours show χ_s distributions (kPa): (a) Typical sand (case 3, case 4), (b)**
 506 **Typical silty clay (case 5, case 6).**

507 The steepness of the curvilinear segments below the vertical segments do not differ
 508 significantly for the typical sand but vary widely for the typical silty clay between drying and
 509 wetting states due to the magnitude of χ_s movement between these two conditions, which is
 510 lower in the typical sand than in the typical silty clay. During steady state infiltrative condition
 511 (cases 3 and 5), the absolute magnitude of χ_s and the variations of χ_s are limited in both the
 512 typical sand (path A₃-D₃ in Fig. 10(c)) and the typical silty clay (path A₅-D₅ in Fig. 10(c)), the
 513 curvilinear segment being steeper for the typical sand (Fig. 9(a)) than for the typical silty clay
 514 (Fig. 9(b)) reflects a strong influence of the friction angle in governing the slope shape ($\varphi' =$
 515 40° for the typical sand compared to $\varphi' = 25^\circ$ for the typical silty clay).

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Figure 10. Variation of χs with h_0 and contribution of χs to the stability of a vertically faced soil layer: (a) Variation of χs with h_0 based on Eq. 31, (b) χs of a limiting vertically faced soil layer of 4 m height located at the top of a riverbank ($\gamma_t = 17 \text{ kN/m}^3$) based on

Eq. 21 derived by lower bound limit plasticity (Chen and Scawthorn, 1970; Michalowski, 2013), (c) χ s applied at the top boundary (AD) in analysis cases 3-6 (case number shown as subscript) given by the χ model of Eq. 19 (Khalili and Khabbaz, 1998).

3.3. Controlling potential volume loss from mass failure and sediment runoff between initial and steady state unsaturated conditions

Let V_i denote the volume of soil (per m length of riverbank) between an initial state (steady state flow, non-limiting equilibrium stress) and an equilibrated infiltration state (steady state infiltration flow, limiting equilibrium stress). Similarly, let V_{ss} denote the volume of soil between an equilibrated infiltration state and an equilibrated evaporation state. These quantities, due to mass conservation and an assumed constant bulk density for each soil, can be considered potentially erodible (i.e., being transported from within the system boundary (Fig. 1) to the outside), and for the typical sand and the typical silty clay (of sufficiently high permeability) in cases 3-6 (Table 1, Table 2), are graphically illustrated in Fig. 11. For the given failure mechanism (Fig. 1) and adopted parameters (Table 1, Table 2), the potential volume losses V_i and V_{ss} in Fig. 11 should be considered as upper bounds to physically mobilizable sediment volumes because several features such as partial failure, internal deformation, and sediment storage within the bank have not been incorporated into the analysis. Moreover, V_{ss} in Fig. 11 was obtained for hydraulic states on the main drying and wetting paths; thus, it should be greater than the V_{ss} obtained from a corresponding analysis with flow states traversing the drying-wetting scanning paths (with insignificant void ratio changes). It can be calculated that $V_i=5.34 \text{ m}^3$, $V_{ss}=1.56 \text{ m}^3$ per m run of the typical sand riverbank (Fig. 11(a)) and $V_i=5.66 \text{ m}^3$, $V_{ss}=2.34 \text{ m}^3$ per m run of the typical silty clay riverbank (Fig. 11(b)). For the typical sand and typical silty clay parameters adopted in these analyses, the values obtained are significant (particularly those of V_{ss} , since the values of V_i may depend on initial slope design). These V_{ss} values of 1.56 m^3 and 2.34 m^3 per m run could be compared with *in situ* estimates gathered of actively eroding European riverbanks from the literature listed in Table 3. They show measured lateral retreat rates of up to $0.55 \text{ m/m run/17 months}$ (Thorne, 1978), 0.8 m/m run/year (Augustowski and Kukulak, 2021) and $1.17 \text{ m/m run/year}$ (Jugie et al., 2018), and volume loss rate (over relevant monitoring periods) of up to $2.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{m run}$ (Casagli et al., 1999), $3.51 \text{ m}^3/\text{m run}$ (Luppi et al., 2008) and $1.47 \text{ m}^3/\text{m run}$ (Klösch et al., 2011). It should be noted that major changes in the riverbank environment can occur over many years and decades, actively eroding riverbanks might become temporarily stable while temporarily stable

555 riverbank might become actively eroding, resulting in smaller long-term average bank retreat
556 estimates than those listed in Table 3. For example, the measured 2006/2007-2009/2010 (i.e.,
557 over approximately 3-4 years) maximum bank retreat rates for the 9 study sites along the River
558 Stour (East Anglia, England, UK) reported by Anstead (2012) (Table 3) were on average 4.2
559 times larger than their corresponding 1903/1904-1962/1981 (i.e., over approximately 58-78
560 years) rates obtained from historical maps.

561 V_i could potentially be controlled with suitable engineering design. One common approach is
562 to incorporate a factor of safety (FS) greater than 1 into this coupled analysis by reducing the
563 soil strength parameters (Bishop, 1955; Dawson et al., 1999) according to:

$$564 \quad FS = \frac{c'}{c'_m} = \frac{\tan \varphi'}{\tan \varphi'_m} \quad (28)$$

565 where c'_m, φ'_m are reduced effective soil cohesion and reduced effective soil friction angle,
566 respectively. By varying FS, different designs of non-limiting curvilinear slopes (Vo and
567 Russell, 2017; Nandi and Ghosh, 2024) can be obtained, which have been shown to offer
568 superior erosion resistance compared to planar and convex slopes (Young and Mutchler, 1969a,
569 1969b; Meyer and Kramer, 1969; Rieke-Zapp and Nearing, 2005; Schor and Gray, 2007; Jeldes
570 et al., 2014b), and can account for 2D steady state unsaturated flow field.

571 On the other hand, V_{ss} is difficult to estimate and control due to the dynamic and complex
572 nature of flow boundary conditions. Indeed, the studies summarised in Table 3 demonstrate the
573 need to carefully consider a range of local factors which can affect the flow boundary
574 conditions at any site, e.g., discharge events (Casagli et al., 1999; Luppi et al., 2008; Anstead,
575 2012), land use and the degree of channelisation (Kronvang et al., 2012), bank vegetation
576 (Anstead, 2012; Kronvang et al., 2012), frost action (Thorne, 1978; Veihe et al., 2011;
577 Augustowski and Kukulak, 2021) to identify accurately the governing factor(s) and the time(s)
578 when most soil volume lost (due to mass failure and/or surface erosion) estimated to have
579 occurred. When those factor(s) are appropriately considered, the approach adopted in this study
580 could provide engineers with a reasonably simple way of estimating bounds on the soil mass
581 potentially erodible from riverbanks by a rotational failure mode due to wetting-drying cycles
582 (i.e., $(V_i + V_{ss})\rho_t$ where ρ_t is the soil bulk density (kg/m^3)), a key input of process-based sediment
583 yield estimation in waterbodies (Simon and Darby, 1999; Zhao et al., 2022). To calculate how
584 much of the yielded sediment and sediment-borne pollutants such as pesticides might become
585 water mobile and be transported from their sources, additional empirical data are needed on

586 river and riverbed morphology, water balance and flow dynamics, water quality and pesticide
 587 characteristics, much of which are site and substance specific, and are outside the scope of this
 588 study.

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591 **Figure 11. Slope profiles showing potentially erodible soil volumes between different**
 592 **conditions (h_0 is the maximum height of a limiting vertically faced cracked soil layer**
 593 **governed by Eq. 21, χ_s variation over the long term will change h_0): (a) Typical sand**
 594 **(case 3, case 4), (b) Typical silty clay (case 5, case 6).**

595

Table 3. Erosion estimates of some European riverbanks reported in the literature.

Study	Location and monitoring period	Bank profile and bank soil properties	Climatic and hydrological conditions	Erosion measurement technique	Bank retreat rate or eroded volume
Thorne, C. R. (1978)	Morfodion sites along the River Severn (Wales, UK) from June 1975 to November 1976	<p>Distance from top of bank to river bed level was < 2.3 m at monitoring sites.</p> <p>Bank soil profile consisted of non-cohesive layer(s) (sand, gravel) overlain by a cohesive layer (silt, clay):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-cohesive layer(s) had maximum bank angles of approximately 45° • $c'=11-18$ kPa and $\varphi'=25^\circ-32.5^\circ$ were obtained from consolidated drained triaxial compression testing of samples from the cohesive layer. 	<p>Maritime climate with frequent precipitation throughout the year (no markedly wet/dry season), average annual rainfall was up to 2400 mm near the river source (the Plynlimon massif). River discharge (1994-1996) at medium flow levels increased rapidly from the source, from 0.03 m³/s at 0.08 km to 4.44 m³/s at 32.5 km (Lawler et al., 1997). Channel width was approximately 13 to 48 m (Atkinson and Davis, 2000).</p>	<p>Erosion pins (installed horizontally and vertically), surveying and mapping</p>	<p>At Morfodion sites, non-cohesive banks eroded at an average rate of 0.385-0.55 m lateral retreat/m run, much higher than cohesive banks at a rate of approximately 0.02 m lateral retreat/m run.</p>
Casagli, N. et al. (1999)	<p>A streambank of the River Sieve located at the Fornacina gauging station (Tuscany, Italy) from February 1996 to July 1997</p>	<p>Bank soil profile consisted of 2 layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A basal sandy gravel layer of 1.7 m thick which can be divided into 2 thinner units with different friction angles and resistance to surface erosion • A sandy silt upper layer of 2.5 m thick and has $\varphi'=33^\circ$, $c'=0$ 	<p>Mediterranean climate with 1 minimum precipitation (in July) and 2 maximum precipitations (the 1st in November and the 2nd at the end of winter), average annual rainfall (1921-1980) was 1000 to 1400 mm. Average of mean daily discharge (1931-1993) was 15.7 m³/s (channel width of 64 m).</p>	<p>Erosion pins (installed horizontally) and marked pebbles, surveying and mapping</p>	<p>The volume eroded was approximately 2.6 m³/ m run (=2 m³/m run of the sandy silt upper layer + 0.6 m³/ m run of the basal sandy gravel layer) from a streambank cross-section (which was mapped between 1 December 1995 and 28 March 1997). Surface erosion events were</p>

		kPa (obtained from consolidated drained triaxial compression tests) and $k_{sat}=6*10^{-6}$ m/s (obtained from <i>in situ</i> seepage tests).			found to be much more frequent than mass failures. Reductions in matric suction were observed on many occasions and could represent an effective trigger for bank instability.
Luppi, L. et al. (2008)	500 m long study site (including an actively eroding segment of about 70 m in length) of the River Cecina (Tuscany, Italy) from autumn 2003 to summer 2004	Measured from a fixed and flat river bed level, the eroding bank within the study site was approximately 5-5.5 m in height and consisted of a distinct upper portion (sandy silt, massive sandy silt, silty sand and clay) overlying a 1.85-2.25 m thick gravel toe (gravel, gravel and cobbles). Strength parameters $c'=3.3-4.7$ kPa, $\varphi'=33^{\circ}-45^{\circ}$ were adopted for the distinct upper portion materials in their numerical modelling.	Mediterranean climate with a dry season and highly variable precipitation, average annual rainfall is about 944 mm. Mean daily discharge at nearby gauging station was 7.61 m ³ /s (channel width of 45–150 m).	Erosion pins (installed horizontally and vertically), surveying and mapping	During the monitoring period, 7 erosive flow events were identified and measured. Eroded volumes were 2.81, 3.51, 0.18, 0.57, 2.64, 2.78, 0.14 m ³ /m run for event no. 1 to 7, respectively. Total volume eroded was 12.63 m ³ /m run for the period. Both surface erosion and mass failures were major contributors to the total eroded amount.
Klösch, M. et al. (2011)	50 m long riverbank segment of the River Mur (Gosdorf, Austria) from May 2007 to December 2008	The riverbanks of the restored section consist of gravel (≈ 0.5 m) overlain by silty sand of varying thickness. Sandy soils were weakly cohesive but were at unsaturated conditions and would quickly erode by incision. A representative cross section (measured in 2006 at km 114.840 downstream) was	Continental climate with relatively consistent rainfall throughout the year (higher precipitation in summer, some snowfalls in winter), average annual rainfall is about 800 to 900 mm. Mean discharge was 150 m ³ /s. Highest discharges occurred during snowmelt in May, and second flow	A comprehensive monitoring program was undertaken. Terrestrial photogrammetry was used to create digital elevation models at 4 different dates to	Flow events on 6 June, 24 July and 16 August 2008 with peak discharges of around 463, 357, 491 m ³ /s, respectively, introduced 1.08, 1.36, 1.47 m ³ /m run, respectively, to the channel due to bank erosion. Due to these 3 events, the eroded gravels (1.81

		approximately 5.4 to 6.4 m in (bankfull) height and had a slope of 30°.	peaks occurred in July/August. Channel width (measured in 2006 at km 114.840 downstream) was approximately 96.5 m.	measure the eroded sediment volumes corresponding to 3 flow events.	m ³ /m run) rested on the river bed while finer sediments (2.1 m ³ /m run) would likely be removed over time.
Veihe, A. et al. (2011)	A streambank site located within the 16 km ² catchment of Harrested stream (Zealand, Denmark) from 2004 to 2008	The average distance from bottom of stream to top of bank is 1.8 m with a bank angle of approximately 40°. The vegetation on the streambank is dominated by grasses and herbaceous plants. Surface soil can be characterised as sandy loam and subsurface soils as loam/clay loam.	Maritime climate with continuous precipitation throughout the year (highest in autumn), average annual rainfall was 717 mm (205 mm ends up as stream discharge). On average, frost occurred 87 days/year, temperature below freezing point for 24 hours occurred 17 days/year. Average streambed width is 1.7 m at the studied site.	Erosion pins (including 1 of photo-electronic type) (installed horizontally), surveying and mapping	Erosion rates of > 0.05 m lateral retreat/m run/year were measured at the lower parts of the bank and were associated with surface erosion. Low soil moisture content and low stream discharge triggered mass failure during dry periods (springs of 2004 and 2005), as probably did freeze–thaw cycles during winters.
Anstead, L. (2012)	9 study sites along the River Stour (East Anglia, England, UK) from 2006 to 2010	Banks at all 9 sites were characterised by steep slopes with no woody vegetation. Materials at 8 of out the 9 sites were cohesive (silt, clay), material at 1 site (at Nayland) was non-cohesive (primarily gravel). Bank height is 1.8 m at both site S1 (in Sudbury) and site N1 (in Nayland).	Maritime climate with wetter conditions in autumn and winter months, average annual rainfall of the whole catchment (1044 km ²) was 586 mm. Bankfull discharge was 34.1 m ³ /s at site S1 and 38.77 m ³ /s at site N1. Channel width/depth ratio is 13.68 at site S1 and 9.57 at site N1.	Photo-electronic erosion pins (installed horizontally), surveying and mapping	The 1 non-cohesive bank site eroded at an average rate of 0.208 m lateral retreat/m run/year, much higher than the 8 cohesive bank sites at an average rate of 0.034–0.102 m lateral retreat/m run/year.
Kronvang, B. et al. (2012)	36 study sites (randomly selected,	The typical landscape of the study sites featured moraine plains underlain by	Maritime climate with wetter conditions in summer and autumn	Erosion pins (installed	During the monitoring period, the average erosion rate was 0.031 m

	each 100 m in length) in the catchment area of the River Odense (Funen, Denmark) from 2006 to 2009	moraine clay. The most common soil types were loamy sandy soils (40%) and sandy clay soils (36%).	months, the average annual precipitation of the study sites was 740 mm. Mean annual discharge (mostly 1989–2001 data) was between 0.45 and 6.45 m ³ /s at 7 gauging stations (Thodsen, 2007).	horizontally), surveying and mapping	lateral retreat/m run/year. Bank erosion amounted to 18-25% of the annual total Phosphorus export from the River Odense catchment.
Jugie, M. et al. (2018)	6 study reaches along 13 km of the River Merantaise (in southern Île-de-France, France) over a 16 months period (June 2013 – December 2014)	Across the 6 studied sites, bank soils comprised sand (38%), silt (55%) and clay (7%) and were considered homogenous over their vertical profiles, very few stratigraphical variations were observed. Bank height ranges from 1.2 m at study site 2 to 2.4 m at study site 6.	Maritime climate with consistent rainfall throughout the year, the average annual precipitation of the catchment area was 700 mm. The inter-annual mean discharge (2011-2014) was around 0.05 m ³ /s, and the maximum peak discharge (measured since 2012) was 2.85 m ³ /s. Channel width ranged from 2.5 to 8 m at the 6 studied reaches.	At each of the 6 studied sites, between 9 and 12 erosion pins were installed horizontally along 3 to 4 vertical profiles. SfM photogrammetry survey was also conducted at the studied site no. 4.	It was concluded that bank erosion was locally very heterogeneous during the monitoring period. Lateral retreat rates were measured to range from 0.01 m to 1.17 m/m run/year. 3 out of 6 studied sites retreated significantly at 0.25 to > 1 m/m run/year. The bottom of the bank was the most active part in terms of erosional activities.
Augustowski, K. and Kukulak, J. (2021)	5 study sites along the River Wielki Rogoźnik and its tributaries (Podhale, Poland) from November 2013 to October 2014	Banks at all 5 sites were not protected by vegetation, distance from top of bank to water level was 1.8-3 m. Bank soil profile at all 5 sites consisted of an approximately 0.75-2.45 m thick cohesive layer (silt, clay, with some sand) overlying a non-cohesive layer (gravel, sand, with some silt and clay).	Continental climate, higher precipitation in summer with significant snowfall in winter, the average annual rainfall was 600-1200 mm in Podhale. Mean discharge was approximately 1.9 m ³ /s (channel width was 7-10 m on average). Ground under snow cover occurred	Erosion pins (installed horizontally), surveying and mapping	Average erosion rate due to fluvial processes was 0.165-0.8 m lateral retreat/m/year run across site nos. 1, 2, 4, 5, but was only 0.08 m lateral retreat/m run at site no. 3. In comparison, average erosion rate due to frost processes (especially cyclic freezing and

		At site no. 3, a basement of Neogene clay (a 0.5 m thick sandy clay layer) was found to locate below the gravelly sandy layer.	100-110 days/year, rivers under ice cover occurred 70-100 days/year.		thawing) was between -0.022 and 0.404 m lateral retreat/m run.
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597

598 4. Conclusion

599 This study assesses how varying unsaturated flow conditions impact mass failure and surface
600 erosion and govern the shape of homogenous soil slope over time. To this end, an original
601 semi-analytical framework has been developed to integrate a 2D unsaturated flow solution of
602 Richards' equation into a slip line theory based- limiting equilibrium analysis of slopes. The
603 framework has been applied to the boundary value problem of a typical European riverbank
604 segment by idealising it initially as a trapezoidal domain and subjecting it to two analyses: (i)
605 steady and transient state flows (the transient state investigation was conducted to estimate how
606 long it takes a typical silty clay bank to reach steady state condition), and (ii) coupled steady
607 state flow-limiting equilibrium stress. Analysis (i) is to assess the magnitude and distribution
608 of matric head around the crest of a typical sand slope and a typical silty clay slope, and how
609 they are impacted by the riverbank dimension b , flow boundary conditions (ψ_s and ψ_t
610 functions) and the saturated hydraulic conductivity k_{sat} . Analysis (ii) is to investigate how an
611 initially linear slope could change to a curvilinear profile via a rotational failure mechanism,
612 releasing a significant soil volume from its surface, an amount that can potentially be washed
613 into rivers and pollute the aquatic environment. The most important findings of this study can
614 be summarised as follows:

- 615 • The steady state solution of Richards' equation for 2D unsaturated flow can be
616 integrated with the Mohr-Coulomb limiting equilibrium condition to analyse the
617 stability and geometry of a typical riverbank segment. The implementation of this
618 coupling was carried out using standard numerical methods, and for the relevant cases
619 (case nos. 3-7) a few iterations were needed to achieve satisfactory convergence on the
620 geometry. Whereas previous works on earth pressure and stability problems involving
621 unsaturated soils have often assumed 1D unsaturated flow, this work is the first to
622 consider coupling 2D unsaturated flow fields with a slip line theory based- elastoplastic
623 model to quantify potential bounds of soil volume lost from riverbank slopes caused by
624 mass failure and surface erosion. This approach is amenable to overhanging geometry
625 (Vo and Russell, 2020) and axisymmetric effects (Vo et al., 2022) but not for 3D effects.
- 626 • The problem geometry and flow boundary conditions proposed by Tracey and
627 Vahedifard (2023) is found to be suitable for calibrating this riverbank analysis. Apart
628 from the exponential form of the Gardner (1958) model, the riverbank dimension b and
629 flow boundary conditions (ψ_s and ψ_t functions) are found to have strong impacts on

630 the pattern of matric head distribution within the riverbank body. This highlights the
631 need to consider 2D unsaturated flow field (rather than 1D unsaturated flow field) in
632 carrying out limiting equilibrium analyses involving unsaturated soils whenever
633 possible. It should be noted that although b is relatively straightforward to
634 measure/approximate *in situ*, obtaining accurate ψ_s and ψ_t functions for steady state
635 infiltrative and evaporative conditions could be challenging as they are highly
636 dependent on many dynamic and local factors, including ground water table
637 fluctuations, river inflow and discharge, climatic conditions and impacts of engineering
638 interventions. The transient state analyses conducted on the typical silty clay with
639 $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-7}$ m/s shows that achieving steady state matric head fields takes > 30 days
640 (the condition for which is unlikely to be sustained when compared with occurrence
641 intervals of significant flux events (e.g., fluctuating inflows and discharges, seasonal
642 flow cycles) in many European river systems), clearly demonstrating the complexity of
643 establishing steady state flow conditions in soils with low permeability.

- 644 • The potentially erodible soil volumes per m run, calculated for the adopted riverbank
645 geometry and typical sand and typical silty clay (of sufficiently high permeability)
646 parameters, are found to be significant and comparable with upper bounds of *in situ*
647 estimates of some actively eroding European riverbanks from the literature. In
648 particular, the potentially eroded soil volumes, V_{ss} , of around 1.5-2.5 m³ per m run for
649 a 4 m height riverbank (arising from moisture movements between steady state
650 infiltrative and evaporative conditions) underscore the importance of wetting-drying
651 cycles as environmental loadings on soil that drive mass failure and surface erosion of
652 riverbanks and thereby contribute to the pollution of waterways.
- 653 • During steady state infiltration, the steepness of curvilinear profiles at the limiting
654 equilibrium condition is strongly influenced by soil mechanical parameters, as
655 curvilinear slopes are permitted to be steeper in typical sand ($\varphi' = 40^\circ$) than in typical
656 silty clay ($\varphi' = 25^\circ$), despite higher overall χ_s values in the typical silty clay (Fig. 9).
657 In fact, although fine-grained soils such as the typical silty clay may exhibit high
658 suction, they may also be susceptible to volumetric changes (shrinkage/swelling) and
659 desiccation cracking, and are vulnerable to hydro-mechanical degradation in the long
660 term (Thorne, 1978; Wei, 2026). For example, in this study, χ_s in the typical silty clay
661 during steady state evaporation permits a vertically faced layer of significant height (h_0
662 ≥ 4 m in case 6) to theoretically exist. A significant volume this soil ($V_{\text{ss}}=2.34$ m³)

663 could potentially be eroded by hydro-mechanical degradation (as cracks create
664 preferential flow paths during wetting events, lower factor of safety and contribute to
665 mass failure) when the soil's moisture state changes from steady state evaporative to
666 infiltrative conditions. Such a change has indeed been observed *in situ* and pointed out
667 by several researchers, e.g., Casagli et al. (1999) as a trigger of instability and mass
668 failure in fine-grained soils.

669 **List of symbols**

670	a, b	length of base and top of an idealised trapezoidal riverbank segment
671	α	soil constant in the model of Gardner (1958)
672	c', c'_m	effective soil cohesion, reduced effective soil cohesion
673	c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4	coefficients of side and top flow boundary condition function
674	$\chi, \chi^s, (\chi^s)_{OE}$	effective stress parameter, contribution of suction to the effective stress,
675		contribution of suction to the effective stress on segment OE
676	η, ξ	families of stress characteristic curves
677	γ_t, γ_w	bulk unit weight of soil, unit weight of water
678	h_0	height of a vertically faced soil layer located at the top of a riverbank
679	k, k_r, k_{sat}	hydraulic conductivity, relative and saturated hydraulic conductivity
680	L	height of an idealised trapezoidal riverbank segment
681	$n_{vG}, m_{vG}, \alpha_{vG}$	van Genuchten 1980 model parameters
682	φ', φ'_m	effective soil friction angle, reduced effective soil friction angle
683	$\psi, \psi_t, \psi_b, \psi_s$	matric head, matric head at the top, bottom and side of an idealised
684		trapezoidal riverbank segment
685	$\bar{\psi}$	transformed potential of matric head
686	q, q_{OE}	surcharge, surcharge on segment OE
687	ρ_t	bulk density of soil
688	S_e	effective degree of saturation
689	$s, s_e, s_{ae}, s_{ex}, s_r$	soil suction, soil suction value separating saturated and unsaturated states, air
690		entry suction, air expulsion suction, residual suction
691	t	time
692	σ'_m	mean effective stress

693	$\theta, \theta_r, \theta_s$	volumetric water content, residual volumetric water content, saturated
694		volumetric water content
695	θ_p	angle between the major principal stress direction and the vertical
696	V_i, V_{ss}	volume of potentially erodible soil between an initial slope geometry and an
697		equilibrated infiltrative slope geometry, volume of potentially erodible soil
698		between equilibrated evaporative and infiltrative slope geometries
699	v	steady state flow rate
700	x, z	the horizontal, the vertical

701 **Acknowledgements**

702 The financial support of the European Union's Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie
703 Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (H2020-MSCA-RISE) project RECYCLE under
704 grant agreement No 872607 is gratefully acknowledged. The 1st author would also like to thank
705 Dr Thomas Hubble at the University of Sydney for his discussions on the topic.

706 **Competing interests**

707 The authors declare there are no competing interests.

708 **Data Availability Statement**

709 Data generated or analysed during this study are provided in full within the published article.

710 References

- 711 • Anstead, L. (2012). *River bank erosion rates and the case for willow spiling as a bank*
712 *stabilisation solution*. PhD thesis, School of Environmental Sciences, University of
713 East Anglia, Norwich, UK.
- 714 • Ao, C., Zeng, W., Yang, P., Xing, W., Lei, G., Wu, J., Huang, J. (2021). The effects of
715 slope shape and polyacrylamide application on runoff, erosion and nutrient loss from
716 hillslopes under simulated rainfall. *Hydrological Processes*, 35, paper no. e14130.
717 <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.14130>.
- 718 • Atkinson, T. C. and Davis, P. M. (2000). Longitudinal dispersion in natural channels:
719 I. Experimental results from the River Severn, U.K. *Hydrology and Earth System*
720 *Sciences*, 4(3): 345–353. <https://doi.org/10.5194/hess-4-345-2000>.
- 721 • Augustowski, L., Kukulak, J. (2021). The role of frost processes in the retreat of river
722 banks. *Water*, 13(13), paper no. 1812, <https://doi.org/10.3390/w13131812>.
- 723 • Baena-Escudero, R., Rinaldi, M., García-Martínez, B., Guerrero-Amador, I. C., Nardi,
724 L. (2019). Channel adjustments in the lower Guadalquivir River (southern Spain) over
725 the last 250 years. *Geomorphology*, 337 (15 July 2019):15-30.
726 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2019.03.027>.
- 727 • Bennett, E. R., Moore, M. T., Cooper, C. M., Smith, S., Shields, F. D., Drouillard, K.
728 G., Schulz, R. (2009). Vegetated agricultural drainage ditches for the mitigation of
729 pyrethroid-associated runoff. *Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry*, 24(9): 2121–
730 2127. <https://doi.org/10.1897/04-357R.1>.
- 731 • Bishop, A. W. (1955). The use of the slip circle in the stability analysis of slopes.
732 *Géotechnique*, 5(1): 7–17. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1955.5.1.7>.
- 733 • Bishop, A. W. (1959). The principle of effective stress. *Teknisk Ukeblad*, 106(39): 859-
734 863.
- 735 • Bishop, A. W. (1961). The measurement of pore pressure in the triaxial test. In:
736 *Proceedings of Conference on Pore Pressure and Suction in Soils* (pp. 38-46).
737 Butterworth, London, UK.
- 738 • Bruthans J., Soukup J., Vaculikova J., Filippi, M., Schweigstillova, J., Mayo, A. L.,
739 Masin, D., Kletetschka, G., Rihosek, J. (2014). Sandstone landforms shaped by
740 negative feedback between stress and erosion. *Nature Geoscience*, 7(8):597-601.
741 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ngeo2209>.

- 742 • Casagli, N., Rinaldi, M., Gargini, A., Curini, A. (1999). Pore water pressure and
743 streambank stability: results from a monitoring site on the Sieve river, Italy. *Earth*
744 *Surface Processes and Landforms*, 24(12): 1095-1114.
745 [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1096-9837\(199911\)24:12<1095::AID-
746 ESP37>3.0.CO;2-F](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1096-9837(199911)24:12<1095::AID-ESP37>3.0.CO;2-F).
- 747 • Chassiot, L., Lajeunesse, P., Bernier, J. F. (2020). Riverbank erosion in cold
748 environments: review and outlook. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 207, paper no. 103231.
749 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2020.103231>.
- 750 • Chen, W. F., Scawthorn, C. R. (1970). Limit analysis and limit equilibrium solutions
751 in soil mechanics. *Soils and Foundations*, 10(3): 13-49.
752 https://doi.org/10.3208/sandf1960.10.3_13.
- 753 • Chen, W. F. (1975). *Limit analysis and soil plasticity*. Elsevier Scientific, New York ,
754 USA.
- 755 • Cooper, R. J., Hiscock, K. M. (2023). Two decades of the EU Water Framework
756 Directive: evidence of success and failure from a lowland arable catchment (River
757 Wensum, UK). *Science of the Total Environment*, 869 (15 April 2023), paper no.
758 161837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.161837>.
- 759 • Cotton, C. A. (1952). The erosional grading of convex and concave slopes. *The*
760 *Geographical Journal*, 118(2): 197-204. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1791949>.
- 761 • Dawson, E. M., Roth, W. H., Drescher, A. (1999). Slope stability analysis by strength
762 reduction. *Géotechnique*, 49(6): 835–840. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1999.49.6.835>.
- 763 • de Lima, J. L. M. P., Isidoro, J. M. G. P., de Lima, M. I. P., Singh, V. P. (2018).
764 Longitudinal hillslope shape effects on runoff and sediment loss: laboratory flume
765 experiments. *Journal of Environmental Engineering*, 144(2), pp. 04017097-1 to
766 04017097-11. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)EE.1943-7870.0001302](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)EE.1943-7870.0001302).
- 767 • Duró, G., Crosato, A., Kleinhans, M. G., Winkels, T. G., Woolderink, H. A. G.,
768 Uijttewaal, W. S. K. (2019). Distinct patterns of bank erosion in a navigable regulated
769 river. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 45(2): 361-374.
770 <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4736>.
- 771 • Duró, G., Crosato, A., Kleinhans, M. G., Roelvink, D., Uijttewaal, W. S. J. (2020).
772 Bank erosion processes in regulated navigable rivers. *JGR Earth Surface*, 125(7), paper
773 no. e2019JF005441. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JF005441>.

- 774 • European Council (2000). Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the
775 Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field
776 of water policy. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32000L0060)
777 [content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32000L0060](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32000L0060) (accessed March 28th, 2023).
- 778 • European Council (2008). Directive 2008/105/EC of the European Parliament and of
779 the Council of 16 December 2008 on environmental quality standards in the field of
780 water policy, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directives 82/176/EEC,
781 83/513/EEC, 84/156/EEC, 84/491/EEC, 86/280/EEC and amending Directive
782 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. [https://eur-](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008L0105)
783 [lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008L0105](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32008L0105) (accessed March
784 28th, 2023).
- 785 • Fox, G. A., Purvis, R. A., Penn, C. J. (2016). Streambanks: a net source of sediment
786 and phosphorus to streams and rivers. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 181 (1
787 October 2016): 602-614. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2016.06.071>.
- 788 • Gardes, T., Portet-Koltalo, F., Debret, M., Copard, Y. (2021). Historical and post-ban
789 releases of organochlorine pesticides recorded in sediment deposits in an agricultural
790 watershed, France. *Environmental Pollution*, 288, paper no. 117769.
791 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.117769>.
- 792 • Gardner, W. R. (1958). Some steady-state solutions of the unsaturated moisture flow
793 equation with application to evaporation from a water table. *Soil Science*, 85(4): 228-
794 232. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00010694-195804000-00006>.
- 795 • Ghezzehei, T. A., Kneafsey, T. J., Su, G. W. (2007). Correspondence of the Gardner
796 and van Genuchten-Mualem relative permeability function parameters. *Water*
797 *Resources Research*, 43(10), paper no. W10417.
798 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006WR005339>.
- 799 • Gilbert, G. K. (1909). The Convexity of Hilltops. *The Journal of Geology*, 17(4): 344-
800 350. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/30057970>.
- 801 • Griffiths, D. V., Lu, N. (2005). Unsaturated slope stability analysis with steady
802 infiltration or evaporation using elasto-plastic finite elements. *International Journal for*
803 *Numerical and Analytical Methods in Geomechanics*, 29(3): 249-267.
804 <https://doi.org/10.1002/nag.413>.

- 805 • Grove, J. R., Croke, J., Thompson, C. (2013). Quantifying different riverbank erosion
806 processes during an extreme flood event. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*,
807 38(12): 1393-1406. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3386>.
- 808 • Hubble, T. C. T., Docker, B. B., Rutherford, I. D. (2010). The role of riparian trees in
809 maintaining riverbank stability: a review of Australian experience and practice.
810 *Ecological Engineering*, 36(3): 292–304.
811 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoleng.2009.04.006>.
- 812 • Ivanova, A., Wiberg, K., Ahrens, L., Zubcov, E., Dahlberg, A. K. (2021). Spatial
813 distribution of legacy pesticides in river sediment from the Republic of Moldova.
814 *Chemosphere*, 279 (September 2021), paper no. 130923.
815 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130923>.
- 816 • Jeldes, I. A., Vence, N. E., Drumm, E. C. (2014a). Approximate solution to the
817 Sokolovski concave slope at limiting equilibrium. *International Journal of*
818 *Geomechanics*, 15(2):1-8. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GM.1943-5622.0000330](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GM.1943-5622.0000330).
- 819 • Jeldes, I. A., Drumm, E. C., Yoder, E. C. (2014b). Design of stable concave slopes for
820 reduced sediment delivery. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental*
821 *Engineering*, 141(2):1-10. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001211](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001211).
- 822 • Jiang, S. H., Liu, X., Ma, G., Rezaia, M. (2024). Stability analysis of heterogeneous
823 infinite slopes under rainfall-infiltration by means of an improved Green-Ampt model.
824 *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 61(8): 1560–1573. <https://doi.org/10.1139/cgj-2023-0203>.
- 825
- 826 • Jugie, M., Gob, F., Virmoux, C., Brunstein, D., Tamisier, V., Le Coeur, C., Grancher,
827 D. (2018). Characterizing and quantifying the discontinuous bank erosion of a small
828 low energy river using structure-from-motion photogrammetry and erosion pins.
829 *Journal of Hydrology*, 563 (August 2018): 418-434.
830 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2018.06.019>.
- 831 • Khalili, N., Zargarbashi, S. (2010). Influence of hydraulic hysteresis on effective stress
832 in unsaturated soils. *Géotechnique*, 60(9): 729–734.
833 <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.09.T.009>.
- 834 • Khalili, N., Khabbaz, M. H. (1998). A unique relationship for χ for the determination
835 of the shear strength of unsaturated soils. *Géotechnique*, 48(5): 681-687.
836 <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1998.48.5.681>.

- 837 • Klösch, M., Hornich, R., Baumann, N., Puchner, G., Habersack, H. (2011). Mitigating
838 channel incision via sediment input and self-initiated riverbank erosion at the Mur
839 River, Austria. In: *Stream Restoration in Dynamic Fluvial Systems: Scientific*
840 *Approaches, Analyses, and Tools* (ed. by Simon, A., Bennett, S. J., Castro, J. M., pp.
841 319-336). American Geophysical Union, Washing, D. C., USA.
842 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010GM000977>.
- 843 • Kronvang, B., Audet, J., Baattrup-Pedersen, A., Jensen, H. S., Larsen, S. E. (2012).
844 Phosphorus load to surface water from bank erosion in a Danish lowland river basin.
845 *Journal of Environmental Quality*, 41(2): 304–313.
846 <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2010.0434>.
- 847 • Lawler, D. M. (1992). Process dominance in bank erosion systems. In: *Lowland*
848 *Floodplain Rivers: Geomorphological Perspectives* (ed. by Carling, P., Petts, G. F., pp.
849 117-143). Wiley, Chichester, UK.
- 850 • Lawler, D. M. (1993). The measurement of river bank erosion and lateral channel
851 change: a review. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 18(9):777-821.
852 <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.3290180905>.
- 853 • Lawler, D. M., Couperthwaite, J., Bull, L. J., Harris, N. M. (1997). Bank erosion events
854 and processes in the Upper Severn basin. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 1(3):
855 523–534. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5194/hess-1-523-1997>.
- 856 • Lespez, L., Viel, V., Rollet, A. J., Delahaye, D. (2015). The anthropogenic nature of
857 present-day low energy rivers in western France and implications for current restoration
858 projects. *Geomorphology*, 251 (15 December 2015): 64-76.
859 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2015.05.015>.
- 860 • Lu, N., Godt, J. W., Wu, D. T. (2010). A closed-form equation for effective stress in
861 unsaturated soil. *Water Resources Research*, 46(5), paper no. W05515.
862 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2009WR008646>.
- 863 • Luppi, L., Rinaldi, M., Teruggi, L. B., Darby, S. E., Nardi, L. (2008). Monitoring and
864 numerical modelling of riverbank erosion processes: a case study along the Cecina
865 River (central Italy). *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 34(4): 530-546.
866 <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.1754>.
- 867 • Malaj, E., von der Ohe, P. C., Grote, M., Kühne, R., Mondy, C. P., Usseglio-Polatera,
868 P., Brack, W., Schäfer, R. B. (2014). Organic chemicals jeopardize the health of

- 869 freshwater ecosystems on the continental scale. *PNAS*, 111(26): 9549–9554.
870 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1321082111>
- 871 • Madarino, A. (2022). Morphological adjustments of the lower Orba River (NW Italy)
872 since the mid-nineteenth century. *Geomorphology*, 410 (1 August 2022), paper no.
873 108280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2022.108280>.
 - 874 • Martín-Moreno, C., Duque, J. F. M., Ibarra, J. M. N., Rodríguez, N. H., Santos, M. Á.
875 S., Castillo, L. S. (2013). Effects of topography and surface soil cover on erosion for
876 mining reclamation: the experimental spoil heap at El Machorro mine (central Spain).
877 *Land Degradation & Development*, 27(2): 145-159. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ldr.2232>.
 - 878 • Meyer, L. D., Kramer, L. A. (1969). Erosion equations predict land slope development.
879 *Agricultural Engineering*, 50: 522–523.
 - 880 • Michalowski, R. L. (2013). Stability assessment of slopes with cracks using limit
881 analysis. *Canadian Geotechnical Journal*, 50(10): 1011-1021.
882 <https://doi.org/10.1139/cgj-2012-0448>.
 - 883 • Moghimi, H. Mousavi Nezhad, M. Huysmans, M. (2025). Glyphosate and Triton X-
884 100 single-competitive sorption–desorption analysis through kinetic and equilibrium
885 frameworks utilizing maximum likelihood method. *Environmental Science and*
886 *Pollution Research*, 32: 25815–25838. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-025-37082-z>.
 - 887 • Moghimi, H. Mousavi Nezhad, M. Huysmans, M. (2026). Transport and competitive
888 sorption-desorption of glyphosate and Triton X-100 in diverse agricultural soils under
889 high flow rates and various concentration ratios. *Journal of Hydrology*, 668: 134972.
890 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2026.134972>.
 - 891 • Morgenstern, N. (1963). Stability charts for earth slopes during rapid drawdown.
892 *Géotechnique*, 13(2): 121–131. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1963.13.2.121>.
 - 893 • Nandi, S., Ghosh, P. (2024). Curvilinear slope profile–based seismic stability for rock
894 slopes using stress characteristics method and generalized Hoek–Brown criterion.
895 *Journal of Engineering Mechanics*, 150(8), paper no. 04024029.
896 <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/JENMDT.EMENG-7624>.
 - 897 • Peng, J., Vahedifard, F. (2023). Passive and active earth pressures in unsaturated soils
898 under transient flow using a curved failure mechanism. *International Journal of*
899 *Geomechanics*, 23 (7), paper no. 04023087. [https://doi.org/10.1061/IJGNAI.GMENG-](https://doi.org/10.1061/IJGNAI.GMENG-80)
900 [80](https://doi.org/10.1061/IJGNAI.GMENG-80).

- 901 • Richard L. A. (1931). Capillary conduction of liquids through porous medium. *Physics*,
902 1(5): 318-333. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1745010>.
- 903 • Rieke-Zapp, D.H., Nearing, M.A. (2005). Slope shape effects on erosion. *Soil Science*
904 *Society of America Journal*, 69(5): 1463–1471. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2005.0015>.
- 905 • Rowe, P. W., Peaker, K. (1965). Passive earth pressure measurements. *Géotechnique*,
906 15(1): 57-78. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.1965.15.1.57>.
- 907 • Ross, D. S., Wemple, B. C., Willson, L. J., Balling, C. M., Underwood, K. L.,
908 Hamshaw, S. D. (2019). Impact of an extreme storm event on river corridor bank
909 erosion and phosphorus mobilization in a mountainous watershed in the northeastern
910 United States. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Biogeosciences*, 124(1):18-32.
911 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018JG004497>.
- 912 • Schor, H. J., Gray, D. H. (2007). *Landforming: An Environmental Approach to Hillside*
913 *Development, Mine Reclamation and Watershed Restoration*. Wiley, Hoboken, New
914 Jersey, USA.
- 915 • Schulz, R., Peall, S. K. C., Hugo, C., Krause, V. (2001). Concentration, load and
916 toxicity of spraydrift-borne azinphos-methyl at the inlet and outlet of a constructed wet-
917 land. *Ecological Engineering*, 18(2): 239–245. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8574(01)00073-8)
918 [8574\(01\)00073-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-8574(01)00073-8).
- 919 • Simon, A., Darby, S. E. (1999). *Incised river channels: Processes, forms, engineering*
920 *and management*, Wiley, New York, USA.
- 921 • Sokolovskii, V. V. (1965). *Statics of granular media* (1st ed.), Pergamon Press, Oxford,
922 UK.
- 923 • Stone, W. W., Gilliom, R. J., Ryberg, K. R. (2014). Pesticides in U.S. streams and
924 rivers: occurrence and trends during 1992–2011. *Environmental Science and*
925 *Technology*, 48(19): 11025–11030. <https://doi.org/10.1021/es5025367>.
- 926 • Surian, N., Rinaldi, M. (2003). Morphological response to river engineering and
927 management in alluvial channels in Italy. *Geomorphology*, 50(4):307-326.
928 [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X\(02\)00219-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0169-555X(02)00219-2).
- 929 • Thodsen, H. (2007). The influence of climate change on stream flow in Danish rivers.
930 *Journal of Hydrology*, 333(2-4): 226– 238.
931 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhydrol.2006.08.012>.
- 932 • Thorne, C. R. (1978). *Processes of bank erosion in river channels*. PhD thesis, School
933 of Environmental Sciences, University of East Anglia, Norwich, UK.

- 934 • Thorne, C. R. (1982). Processes and mechanisms of river bank erosion. In: *Gravel-bed*
935 *Rivers* (ed. by Hey, R. D., Bathurst, J. C., Thorne, C. R., pp. 227-259). Wiley,
936 Chichester, UK.
- 937 • Tracey, F. T. (2006). Clean two- and three-dimensional analytical solutions of
938 Richards' equation for testing numerical solvers. *Water Resources Research*, 42(8),
939 paper no. W08503. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2005WR004638>.
- 940 • Tracy, F. T., Vahedifard, F. (2023). Two-dimensional analytical solution for transient
941 flow in unsaturated soils considering hydromechanical coupling. *Water Resources*
942 *Research*, 59(12), paper no. e2023WR035326.
943 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2023WR035326>.
- 944 • Troncone, A. (2005). Numerical analysis of a landslide in soils with strain-softening
945 behaviour. *Géotechnique*, 55(8): 585-596. <https://doi.org/10.1680/geot.2005.55.8.585>.
- 946 • Vahedifard, F., Leshchinsky, B. A., Mortezaei, K., Lu, N. (2015). Active earth
947 pressures for unsaturated retaining structures. *Journal of Geotechnical and*
948 *Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 141 (11), paper no. 04015048.
949 [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)GT.1943-5606.0001356](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)GT.1943-5606.0001356).
- 950 • van Genuchten, M. T. (1980). A closed-form equation for predicting the hydraulic
951 conductivity of unsaturated soils. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 44(5): 892-
952 898. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1980.03615995004400050002x>.
- 953 • Veihe, A., Jensen, N. H., Schiøtz, I. G., Nielsen, S. L. (2011). Magnitude and processes
954 of bank erosion at a small stream in Denmark. *Hydrological Processes*, 25(10): 1597-
955 1613. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hyp.7921>.
- 956 • Vo, T., Russell, A. R. (2016). Bearing capacity of strip footing on unsaturated soils by
957 the slip line theory. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 74:122-131.
958 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compgeo.2015.12.016>.
- 959 • Vo, T., Russell, A. R. (2017). Stability charts for curvilinear slopes in unsaturated soils.
960 *Soils and Foundations*, 57(4): 543-556. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sandf.2017.06.005>.
- 961 • Vo, T., Russell, A. R. (2020). Contours of saturated and unsaturated overhanging slopes
962 at limiting equilibrium condition. *International Journal for Numerical and Analytical*
963 *Methods in Geomechanics*, 44(1): 93-116. <https://doi.org/10.1002/nag.3008>.
- 964 • Vo, T., Wang, T., Russell, A. R. (2020). The fall cone test in unsaturated soil and
965 tailings pastes. *Géotechnique*, 72(3): 274-281. <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.20.P.128>.

- 966 • Vo, T. L., Mac, T. N., Do, D. M. (2022). Optimising an output of a slip line field using
 967 a chaotic swamp optimisation algorithm. *Géotechnique Letters*, 12(2): 87-94.
 968 <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgele.21.00082>.
- 969 • Wang, Y., Vo, T., Russell, A. R. (2024). Modelling unsaturated silty tailings and the
 970 conditions required for static liquefaction. *Géotechnique*, 74(12): 1377-1389.
 971 <https://doi.org/10.1680/jgeot.22.00074>.
- 972 • Wei, Y., Fan, W., Chen, H., Yu, B., Deng, L., Liang, J. (2026). Macro-micro changes
 973 of clayey loess subjected to wetting-drying cycles and the effect on mechanical
 974 behavior deterioration. *Soil and Tillage Research*, 257, paper no. 106972.
 975 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2025.106972>.
- 976 • Weibel, S. R., Anderson, R. J., Woodward, R. L. (1964). Urban land runoff as a factor
 977 in stream pollution. *Journal (Water Pollution Control Federation)*, 36(7): 914-924.
- 978 • Wilson, C. G., Kuhnle, R. A., Bosch, D. D., Steiner, J. L., Starks, P. J., Tomer, M. D.,
 979 Wilson, G. V. (2008). Quantifying relative contributions from sediment sources in
 980 conservation effects assessment project watersheds. *Journal of Soil and Water
 981 Conservation November*, 63(6): 523-532. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.63.6.523>.
- 982 • Wolfram, J., Stehle, S., Bub, S., Petschick, L. L., Schulz, R. (2021). Water quality and
 983 ecological risks in European surface waters – monitoring improves while water quality
 984 decreases. *Environmental International*, 152, paper no. 106479.
 985 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106479>.
- 986 • Young, R. A., Mutchler, C. K. (1969a). Effect of slope shape on erosion and runoff.
 987 *Transactions of the ASAE*, 12(2): 231–233. <https://doi.org/10.13031/2013.38806>.
- 988 • Young, R. A., Mutchler, C. K. (1969b). Soil movement on irregular slopes. *Water
 989 Resources Research*, 5(5): 1084–1089. <https://doi.org/10.1029/WR005i005p01084>.
- 990 • Zhang, L. L., Fredlund, D. G., Zhang, L. M., Tang, W. H. (2004). Numerical study of
 991 soil conditions under which matric suction can be maintained. *Canadian Geotechnical
 992 Journal*, 41(4): 569-582. <https://doi.org/10.1139/t04-006>.
- 993 • Zhao, K., Coco, G., Gong, Z., Darby, S. E., Lanzoni, S., Xu, F., Zhang, K., Townend,
 994 I. (2022). A review on bank retreat: mechanisms, observations, and modeling. *Review
 995 of Geophysics*, 60(2), paper no. e2021RG000761.
 996 <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021RG000761>.

997 **Figure captions**

- 998 Figure 1. A simplified riverbank system considered for analysis.
- 999 Figure 2. Initial geometry and flow boundary conditions of a riverbank slope: (a) Initial
1000 geometry and flow boundary conditions of a riverbank slope, (b) Typical
1001 variations of matric suction profile in soil far away from the slope edge.
- 1002 Figure 3. Simplified hydraulic conductivity functions and flow boundary conditions
1003 used in analysis: (a) Simplified hydraulic conductivity functions, (b) Side and
1004 top boundary conditions of the typical sand (case 3, case 4), (c) Side and top
1005 boundary conditions of the typical silty clay (case 5, case 6).
- 1006 Figure 4. Steady state geometry and stress boundary conditions of a riverbank slope:
1007 (a) Steady state geometry and stress boundary conditions of a riverbank
1008 slope, (b) Boundary conditions imposed at the slope surface.
- 1009 Figure 5. The iterative calculation procedure (at steady state) adopted in this study
- 1010 Figure 6. Matric head ψ distributions (m) of Tracey and Vahedifard (2023), case 1 and
1011 case 2 (Table 1): (a) at 1 day, (b) at 2 days, (c) at steady state.
- 1012 Figure 7. Matric head ψ distributions (m) of typical sand and typical silty clay: (a)
1013 Typical sand (case 3, case 4) at steady state, (b) Typical silty clay (case 5,
1014 case 6) at steady state, (c) Typical silty clay (case 5, $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-5}$ m/s)
1015 towards steady state, (d) Typical silty clay (case 5, $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-7}$ m/s)
1016 towards steady state, (e) Typical silty clay (case 6, $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-5}$ m/s) towards
1017 steady state, (f) Typical silty clay (case 6, $k_{\text{sat}} = 10^{-7}$ m/s) towards steady
1018 state.
- 1019 Figure 8. Steady state curvilinear slope profiles of case 7 (Table 2): (a) Curvilinear
1020 slope profiles of case 7, Jeldes et al. (2014a) and Vo and Russell (2017),
1021 contours show the χ_s distribution (kPa) of case 7, (b) Iterative sequence to
1022 obtain the final curvilinear slope profile of case 7.
- 1023 Figure 9. Curvilinear slope profiles of typical sand and typical silty clay at steady state
1024 conditions, contours show χ_s distributions (kPa): (a) Typical sand (case 3,
1025 case 4), (b) Typical silty clay (case 5, case 6).

1026 Figure 10. Variation of χ_s with h_0 and contribution of χ_s to the stability of a vertically
1027 faced soil layer: (a) Variation of χ_s with h_0 based on Eq. 31, (b) χ_s of a
1028 limiting vertically faced soil layer of 4 m height located at the top of a
1029 riverbank ($\gamma_t = 17 \text{ kN/m}^3$) based on Eq. 21 derived by lower bound limit
1030 plasticity (Chen and Scawthorn, 1970; Michalowski, 2013), (c) χ_s applied at
1031 the top boundary (AD) in analysis cases 3-6 (case number shown as
1032 subscript) given by the χ model of Eq. 19 (Khalili and Khabbaz, 1998).

1033 Figure 11. Slope profiles showing potentially erodible soil volumes between different
1034 conditions (h_0 is the maximum height of a limiting vertically faced cracked
1035 soil layer, where χ_s variation could potentially cause a mass failure): (a)
1036 Typical sand (case 3, case 4), (b) Typical silty clay (case 5, case 6).

1037

1038 **Table captions**

1039 Table 1. Analysis parameters of flow through initially linear slope.

1040 Table 2. Analysis parameters of flow through curvilinear slope at limiting condition.

1041 Table 3. Erosion estimates of some European riverbanks reported in the literature

1042 **Appendix A**

1043 The change of variable $\bar{\psi} = e^{\alpha\psi} - e^{-\alpha z}$ gives:

1044
$$\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} + \alpha \bar{\psi} = \alpha e^{\alpha\psi} \left(\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} + 1 \right) \quad (\text{A1})$$

1045 The hydraulic conductivity model of Gardner (1958) is combined with the steady state flow
1046 rate v (m/s) on the top boundary ($z=L$) to give:

1047
$$v(x, L) = -k_{\text{sat}} e^{\alpha\psi} \left[\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}(x, L) + 1 \right] \quad (\text{A2})$$

1048 From Eqs. A1 and A2, the top boundary condition in terms of a flow rate function $v(x, L)$ can
1049 be converted to an equivalent top boundary condition in terms of $\bar{\psi}$ as:

1050
$$\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} + \alpha \bar{\psi} = \alpha \frac{v(x, L)}{-k_{\text{sat}}} \quad (\text{A3})$$

1051 The following flow rate function (Tracy and Vahedifard, 2023) is adopted for the top boundary:

1052
$$\frac{v(x, L)}{-k_{\text{sat}}} = c_3 \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{b} \left(x - \frac{a-b}{2} \right) \right] + c_4 \quad (\text{A4})$$

1053 where c_3 and c_4 are constants. The top boundary condition can subsequently be written as:

1054
$$\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} + \alpha \bar{\psi} = \alpha \left\{ c_3 \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{b} \left(x - \frac{a-b}{2} \right) \right] + c_4 \right\} \quad (\text{A5})$$

1055 which requires the flow rate $v(x, L)$ to be specified at 2 locations along the top boundary for
1056 determination.

1057 For examples, if it is specified that at $x=(a-b)/2$ (i.e., point A of Fig. 2(a)), $v(x, L) =$
1058 $v|_{x=(a-b)/2}$ and at $x=a/2$ (i.e., point D in Fig. 2(a)), $v(x, L) = v|_{x=a/2}$, Eq. A4 gives:

1059
$$c_4 = -\frac{v|_{x=(a-b)/2}}{k_{\text{sat}}} \quad (\text{A6})$$

1060
$$c_3 = \frac{v|_{x=(a-b)/2}}{k_{\text{sat}}} - \frac{v|_{x=a/2}}{k_{\text{sat}}} \quad (\text{A7})$$

1061 therefore, the normalised flow rate function v/k_{sat} and the corresponding top boundary
1062 condition $\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} + \alpha \bar{\psi}$ can be written as:

1063
$$\frac{v(x, L)}{k_{\text{sat}}} = -\left(\frac{v|_{x=\frac{a-b}{2}}}{k_{\text{sat}}} - \frac{v|_{x=\frac{a}{2}}}{k_{\text{sat}}} \right) \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{b} \left(x - \frac{a-b}{2} \right) \right] + \frac{v|_{x=(a-b)/2}}{k_{\text{sat}}} \quad (\text{A8})$$

1064
$$\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} + \alpha \bar{\psi} = \alpha \left\{ \left(\frac{v|_{x=(a-b)/2}}{k_{sat}} - \frac{v|_{x=a/2}}{k_{sat}} \right) \sin \left[\frac{\pi}{b} \left(x - \frac{a-b}{2} \right) \right] - \frac{v|_{x=(a-b)/2}}{k_{sat}} \right\} \quad (A9)$$

1065 Eq. A8 can be plotted as shown in Fig. A1 for a typical sand with parameters listed in Table
 1066 A1.

1067 **Table A1. Parameters of Eq. A8 and Eq. A9 for a typical sand.**

Material	Flow condition	k_{sat}	v at $x=(a-b)/2^{\#}$	v at $x=a/2$	$c_3:c_4^{\#\#}$	$\alpha = 1/\left(\frac{S_e}{\gamma_w}\right)$	$c_1:c_2$	$a: b: L$
		(m/s)	(m/s)	(m/s)	(-):(-)	(1/m)	(-):(-)	(m):(m):(m)
Typical sand	Infiltrative	10^{-4}	$-3.14 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0	0.000314:0	3.27	0.051:0	30:22:4
		10^{-3}	$-3.14 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0	0.0000314:0	3.27	0.051:0	30:22:4
	Evaporative	10^{-4}	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0	-0.000115:0	0.981	0.255:6.8	30:22:4
		10^{-3}	$1.15 \cdot 10^{-8}$	0	-0.0000115:0	0.981	0.255:6.8	30:22:4

1068 [#] typical steady state infiltrative and evaporative flow rate values are adopted from Lu and Griffiths (2004).

1069 ^{\#\#} c_4 and c_3 values are evaluated using Eq. A6 and Eq. A7, respectively.

1070

1071 **Figure A1. The normalised flow rate functions given by Eq. A8 for a typical sand ($k_{sat} =$
 1072 10^{-3} m/s, $k_{sat} = 10^{-4}$ m/s) during evaporative condition ($v = 1.15 \cdot 10^{-8}$ m/s) and
 1073 **infiltrative condition ($v = -3.14 \cdot 10^{-8}$ m/s).****

1074 **Appendix B**

1075 Case 1: $s < s_e$, recognising the approximation $s_e \approx \gamma_w/\alpha$ (see Section 2.1),

$$1076 \quad \chi s = -\gamma_w \psi = -\frac{\gamma_w}{\alpha} \ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}) \approx -s_e \ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}) \quad (\text{B1})$$

1077 The derivatives $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z}$ are therefore

$$1078 \quad \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x} = -\gamma_w \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \approx -s_e \left(\frac{\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial x}}{\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}} \right) \quad (\text{B2})$$

$$1079 \quad \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z} = -\gamma_w \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} \approx -s_e \left(\frac{\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} - \alpha e^{-\alpha z}}{\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}} \right) \quad (\text{B3})$$

1080 Case 2: $s \geq s_e$, recognising the approximation $s_e \approx \gamma_w/\alpha$ (see Section 2.1),

$$1081 \quad \chi s = -\gamma_w \alpha^{-0.55} \psi^{0.45} = -\frac{\gamma_w}{\alpha} [\ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z})]^{0.45} \approx -s_e [\ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z})]^{0.45} \quad (\text{B4})$$

1082 The derivatives $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x}$ and $\frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z}$ are therefore

$$1083 \quad \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial x} = -0.45 \gamma_w \alpha^{-0.55} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial x} \approx -0.45 s_e [\ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z})]^{-0.55} \left(\frac{\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial x}}{\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}} \right) \quad (\text{B5})$$

$$1084 \quad \frac{\partial(c' \cot \varphi' + \chi s)}{\partial z} = -0.45 \gamma_w \alpha^{-0.55} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} \approx -0.45 s_e [\ln(\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z})]^{-0.55} \left(\frac{\frac{\partial \bar{\psi}}{\partial z} - \alpha e^{-\alpha z}}{\bar{\psi} + e^{-\alpha z}} \right) \quad (\text{B6})$$